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Business, Economics & Management

- *Accounting & Taxation*
- *Business, Economics & Management (general)*
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THE ECONOMIC MODEL OF SMALL COUNTRIES IN TERMS OF DIGITALISM

Abasov Mir Faraj Ali oqlu

Doctor of Philosophy in Political Sciences, doctoral student of the Azerbaijan University of Tourism and Management in Economics, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7299-2315>

The article deals with a new socio-political and economic formation due to replace the modern system of capitalism designated by the author as digitalism. Using unique elements of its existence, such as Industry 4.0, the new formation of digitalism creates diffusion between the real world and the virtual world. Next, the author classifies the main actors of the new formation with a special emphasis on small countries. The *purpose* and *objectives* of the article are the formulation and solution of economic and political problems facing these actors, on the one hand, and the parallel formation of a model of economic and political behavior of small countries in the modern world and following the approval of the future formation, on the other hand. It lays an emphasis on the fact that the unwillingness or inability of small countries to solve new, emerging challenges and problems might lead to the loss of economic independence or the complete destruction of such countries. The author identifies four directions in the economy and politics that are strategically important for small countries in terms of a new formation. Using various empirical and theoretical *methods* of analysis (abstraction, generalization, comparativism, modeling, classification, etc) with an emphasis on statistical data and a large amount of analytical information, the author modulates the strategy of economic behavior of the so-called small countries offering them partial solutions to problems, or analyzing specific economic cases suited for contemplated tasks. As a *result*, the author points out that the role and significance of a small country in the era of digitalism is directly related to how quickly, adequately and creatively the actor accepts an epoch of changes and what development models he chooses.

The article is analytical in nature to deal with some major points that need classification and subsequent economic and political planning:

1. Decentralization of political forces, acceleration of economic processes, reduction of bureaucracy
2. Food security
 - 2.1. Business transformation. Distress of old formation giant enterprises. Food security consequences.
 - 2.2. Strong and small countries in the struggle for food and related resources.
3. Nanotechnologies and a concentrated economy.
4. Creation of political associations, unions and cartels of small countries in the era of digitalism.

BUDGET MECHANISM OF UKRAINE IN THE CONDITIONS OF MARTIAL LAW

Chugunov Igor

Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor, Head of the Department of Finance, State University of Trade and Economics, Kyiv, Ukraine

Samoshkina Olga

Candidate of Economic Sciences (Ph.D.), Senior Research Officer, Department of Financial Credit and Tax Policy, National Scientific Center "Institute of Agrarian Economics", Kyiv, Ukraine

Maintaining the stability of the country's financial and budgetary system and determining the specifics of budget support for socio-economic development in martial law require further application of the principles of strategic, program-targeted and effective management of budgetary resources to significantly increase the effectiveness of fiscal policy in achieving strategic development priorities. Effective implementation of these principles should take place within the framework of state strategic planning and forecasting of socio-economic development of the country and medium-term program-target budget planning, which allows assessing the relationship between strategic priorities of the country's development in various spheres of public relations and the results of public administrations. Research on the development and implementation of scientifically sound socio-economic policy of the country in martial law, taking into account the criteria of priority, consistency, system, effectiveness and efficiency of state measures are relevant.

Fiscal policy as an effective tool for influencing the dynamics of socio-economic processes in the country should be formed on the basis of state strategic development priorities, the level of effectiveness and efficiency of budget expenditures in various spheres of public activity, and taking into account trends in economic and socio-demographic processes. As the volume and structure of the budget expenditure in program, departmental, functional and economic classifications characterize the list of strategic priorities of the country's development, regulating these indicators, the state is able to implement consistent, systematic and effective budget policy aimed at an effective solution of economic, social and defense needs of the country at a certain stage of its development as well as prevention of negative trends in the medium term.

The budgetary mechanism of socio-economic development of the country in martial law should provide effective and efficient achievement of economic, social and defense priorities of the country, which involves the transition from planning sectorial budget expenditures to budget planning sectorial results from the use of budget funds in public relations. According to Article 95 of the Constitution of Ukraine, the budget system of Ukraine is based on the principles of fair and impartial distribution of public wealth between citizens and territorial communities. The state strives for a balanced budget of Ukraine. The implementation of these principles is extremely important in the martial law of the country.

It is important to improve the theoretical, methodological and practical foundations of medium-term program-targeted planning of budget programs, taking into account the criteria of priority and effectiveness in solving strategic tasks of the country's development in martial law. Further areas of improving the budgetary mechanism of socio-economic development of the country should include: improvement of approaches to assessing the effectiveness of budget programs and the activities of their managers on the ratio of budget costs, efficiency, quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the industry product, and assessment the final socio-economic effect of budget programs in various spheres of public relations; determination the impact of budget expenditures on the indicators and trends in economic,

socio-demographic and defense spheres; improvement the program-targeted distribution of budget funds between their managers in various areas of public relations on the basis of their strategic plans, taking into account the criteria of effectiveness and priority of their activities.

It is essential to increase the efficiency of allocation of financial resources at the level of state policy in martial law, ensure effective implementation of state and local budgets, strict fiscal discipline, increase transparency of public finance management, human resources management in public finance, increase efficiency budget funds. Fiscal policy as an important component of public financial policy should be an adaptive regulator of socio-economic processes, taking into consideration the basic principles of budget architectonics of revenue and expenditure parts of the budget. Funding from the state budget is primarily provided for the needs of the Armed Forces of Ukraine, social payments to the population. According to preliminary estimates, about thirty percent of enterprises have shut down, and forty-five percent have cut production. According to the Ministry of Finance of Ukraine, budget losses amount is more than two billion hryvnias daily. Infrastructure losses are estimated at one hundred and twenty billion dollars a month. If we take into account military losses, increased military and social budget expenditures, government support programs, it is hundreds of billions of dollars. The main task is to preserve the effectiveness of the financial and budgetary system of Ukraine. The fiscal gap is widening every passing day. The European Union has already established a program of macro-financial assistance to Ukraine in the amount of more than one billion two hundred million euros. In order to promptly implementate the needs of the security and defense sectors under martial law, the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine adopted a resolution "On the allocation of funds to the reserve fund of the state budget", which provides for an increase in the reserve fund by more than fifty billion hryvnias. The government has also decided to simplify budget procedures in order to ensure the effective functioning of the budget sphere in martial law. According to the Ministry of Finance of Ukraine and the Ministry of Economy of Ukraine, the loss of gross domestic product is from forty to fifty percent this year. Not only significant external borrowing is important, but also the restructuring of external public debt and payments for its servicing. The government is taking a number of well-founded budget measures, gradually finding an understanding of the balance of the wartime budget, which is important at this stage of fiscal and socio-economic relations in Ukraine.

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**ECOLOGICAL-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF THE SOUTH CAUCASUS
COUNTRIES UNDER THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC**

Teimuraz Shengelia

Doctor of Economic Sciences, Full Professor at Tbilisi State University, Georgia

Khatuna berishvili

Doctor of Economics, Associate Professor at Tbilisi State University, Georgia

David KbilaSvili

Phd, Teacher at Tbilisi State University, Georgia

The Covid-19 crisis, that began in the late of 2019, was declared as a pandemic on March 12, 2020 by the World Health Organization. It has caused enormous damage of human health and the economic development of countries. The consequences of the pandemic, as well as the constraints associated with it, put pressure on health systems, harm free trade, and slow the growth of production, consumption, and investment. The countries of the South Caucasus have accelerated the development of a medium- and long-term national strategy for economic recovery in the post-pandemic period, responding to environmental challenges, creating an „Ecological Economy“.

Environmental measures can ensure the recovery of countries' economies and create jobs. According to experts, the „Ecological Economy“ can create 395 million jobs by the 2030. In this regard, investments in a green infrastructure for the economic growth have a significant potential.

The analysis showed that the measures to overcome COVID-19 in the South Caucasus countries have both positive and negative environmental effects.

In Armenia, 22 measures were taken to reduce the negative impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, one of which, in terms of environmental impact on employment, included the creation of new jobs for planting. Employees of this program received \$ 19,000 in compensation. Given the success of this project, the German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development has supported the implementation of Phase 2 of the program. In Azerbaijan, the number of public sector employees increased from 38,000 to 90,000 to facilitate job creation during the pandemic. Participants in the program were employed in disinfection, social services for vulnerable groups, and the development of urban green spaces. The country has developed an energy efficiency policy program for Azerbaijan and is currently working on a draft National Energy Efficiency Action Plan. Given that the COVID-19 crisis is having a particularly severe impact on small and medium-sized businesses, the countries of the region are refining their national private sector development strategies. It is important that these plans are in relevance with environmental goals, including incentives for business development. Several countries have already included environmental aspects in their SME support measures. The Ministry of Economy of Armenia has organized a series of webinars for entrepreneurs on the topic: "Training Enterprises to Fight against COVID-19". Based on the increase in the volume of grants for micro and small businesses in Georgia, the program "Produce in Georgia" was implemented, that is focused on green, innovative and sustainable business. In order to enhance knowledge and skills related to effective environmental management, economic incentives, incentives for small and medium-sized businesses, a small and medium-sized business ecology program was launched in Azerbaijan.

International partners play an important role against the fight with COVID-19 in the South Caucasus. Despite quarantine restrictions, several pre-pandemic environmental projects continue to be implemented as planned, and new COVID-19 Green Response Initiatives have

been developed. The United Nations Development Program (UNDP) is supporting the South Caucasus countries in developing applications for COVID-19.

Thus, the impact of Covid-19 on the ecological environment in the countries of the South Caucasus is heterogeneous, according to the economic-ecological approaches of the governments of these countries, which are characterized by dynamism and systematicity.

Chemical & Material Science

- *Analytical Chemistry*
- *Biochemistry*
- *Ceramic Engineering*
- *Chemical & Material Sciences (general)*
- *Chemical Kinetics & Catalysis*
- *Combustion & Propulsion*
- *Composite Materials*
- *Corrosion*
- *Crystallography & Structural Chemistry*
- *Dispersion Chemistry*
- *Electrochemistry*
- *Inorganic Chemistry*
- *Materials Engineering*
- *Medicinal Chemistry*
- *Molecular Modeling*
- *Nanotechnology*
- *Oil, Petroleum & Natural Gas*
- *Organic Chemistry*
- *Polymers & Plastics*

**СИНТЕЗ И ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ПОВЕРХНОСТНО- АКТИВНОЙ СОЛИ,
ПОЛУЧЕННОЙ ПО РЕАКЦИИ 1,2- АМИНОЭТАНА С ДОДЕКАНОВОЙ
КИСЛОТОЙ**

Зарбалиева Ильхама Агалар

Институт Нефтехимических Процессов им. Ю.Г. Мамедалиева НАНА Баку, Азербайджан, Ходжалы 30

Алимова Амина Надир

Институт Нефтехимических Процессов им. Ю.Г. Мамедалиева НАНА Баку, Азербайджан, Ходжалы 30

Бадалова Лала Назим

Студент 2-го курса факультета САВАН по специальности «Пищевая Инженерия» Азербайджанского Государственного Экономического Университета

Бабаев Кемаль Расим

Студент 2-го курса факультета САВАН по специальности «Пищевая Инженерия» Азербайджанского Государственного Экономического Университета

Баладжаева Зарифа Вугар

Студент 2-го курса факультета САВАН по специальности «Пищевая Инженерия» Азербайджанского Государственного Экономического Университета

Гулиева Латафат Фахри

Студент 2-го курса факультета САВАН по специальности «Пищевая Инженерия» Азербайджанского Государственного Экономического Университета

Аскеров Ульви Ахад

Студент 2-го курса факультета САВАН по специальности «Пищевая Инженерия» Азербайджанского Государственного Экономического Университета

Гусейнли Нармин Сеймур

Студент 2-го курса факультета САВАН по специальности «Пищевая Инженерия» Азербайджанского Государственного Экономического Университета

В последние годы наряду с бурным развитием нефтяной промышленности наблюдается резкое загрязнение окружающей среды в результате аварий при добыче и переработке нефти. Хотя плотный слой нефти можно очистить механическим способом, но тонкий слой нефти практически очистить невозможно. На сегодняшний день существует большая потребность в совершенствовании коллоидно-химических методов, позволяющих снимать с водной поверхности тонкие слои нефти, а также в создании новых, более эффективных, экологически чистых нефтесобирающих и нефтедиспергирующих реагентов. Научные исследования проводятся для решения вышеуказанных экологических проблем, а также для синтеза и изучения новых поверхностно-активных веществ (ПАВ) с поверхностно-активными и нефтедиспергирующими свойствами.

Представленная работа посвящена синтезу и исследованию новых нефтесобирающих и нефтедиспергирующих реагентов. Синтез нового поверхностно-активного вещества осуществлен на основе 1,2- аминоэтана с додекановой кислотой при их массовых соотношениях 1:1. Время проведения реакции 2-4 часа.

Реакция протекает по нижеприведенной схеме:

Поверхностно-активное свойство соли додекановой кислоты с 1,2 аминоэтаном было определено с помощью тензиометра на границе воздух-вода с использованием их

водных растворов при различных концентрациях в интервале 0.01%-0.5%, при комнатной температуре (25°C). Установлено, что высокую поверхностную активность проявляет соль триэтилентетрамина ($\sigma=20,64 \text{ мН}\cdot\text{м}^{-1}$) при концентрациях (0.3%). Поверхностное натяжение дистиллированной воды на границе с воздухом $72.83 \pm 0,2 \text{ мН}\cdot\text{м}^{-1}$ без реагента.

Структура данного реагента ПАВ позволяет нам определить, что в результате лабораторных исследований на поверхности трёх типов вод различной минерализации: дистиллированная, пресная и морская вода. Используется неразбавленный продукт и 5%-ый водный раствор реагента. При нанесении неразбавленного продукта на нефтяную поверхность дистиллированной воды наблюдается нефтесобирающая способность $K_{\text{max}}=24$, а в 5%-ом растворе наблюдается нефтесобирающая и нефтедиспергирующая способность; при нанесении на поверхности пресной воды разлитой нефтью неразбавленного продукта и 5%-го раствора наблюдается нефтесобирающая и нефтедиспергирующая способность; на поверхности морской воды наблюдается нефтесобирающая и нефтедиспергирующая способность $K_{\text{max}}= 59.7\%$ при нанесении неразбавленного продукта, а при 5%-ом растворе наблюдается нефтесобирающая способность. Продолжительность процесса длилась 16 суток.

Используя эти реагенты рекомендуется можно использовать в различных областях применения (в качестве антикоррозионного ингибитора, противомикробного реагента, а также в качестве нефтесобирающая и нефтедиспергирующая реагента).

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FACE RECOGNITION IN HUMANOID ROBOTS

Megi Kavtaradze

Master's Degree Candidate, Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University, The CEO of Destiny Robotics, Florida, United States, 33131

Lela Mirtskhulava

Associate Professor, Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University, Chief Scientist of Destiny Robotics, Florida, United States, 33131

Humanoid robots are expected to be developed and operate in a close relationship with human beings, serve the needs of people, and work to create a connection between the user and the rest of the world. In order to bridge this gap in technology, these robots must be able to handle the wide variety of emotional states of humans. After years of research on classical computer vision algorithms, it quickly became obvious that face detection systems were a reality. Different Computer vision algorithms managed to achieve very good accuracy in face detection even without utilizing any data or statistical methods. But face detection alone is not a very powerful tool in identifying the person standing in front. But in recent years Google also made face recognition an easy task after introducing Face Net, an approach that could recognize people from a huge database in real-time. The algorithm architecture introduced became very simple and easily understandable compared to the models, which tried very complex systems of multiple stages combined with PCA for dimensionality reduction and then used SVM for assigning classes to each face. Even though Face Net was released in 2015, which with the advancement of Deep Learning models might seem very old, the algorithmic idea that it offered, was so unique and simple that new state of the art models such as can be integrated into the architecture to increase the accuracy while again leaving all the processing in the real-time.

In this section, we will try to explain on a high level how Face Net architecture works. As stated, many times, it is simple. Convolutional neural networks are building blocks of today's computer vision. Even though recent trends of transformer networks in computer vision tasks give promising results, still deep convolutional neural networks remain the most widely used and utilized algorithms for computer vision tasks, such as classification, object detection, segmentation, etc. Face Net also uses basic CNN architecture. It acts as a classification network without a classifier layer, in the end, meaning we don't extract classes but instead are interested in the embedding of the CNN. Extracted embedding represents features of the image. In our case features of the face, such as eye color, nose shape, head shape, etc. So basically, the whole head of the person will be transformed into a much smaller feature space. For example, let's say we have an image of a face that has a resolution of $28 \times 28 \times 3$, meaning its width and height are 28 red, blue, and green pixels. Now we cannot directly compare two images of this size, because it's computationally too complex. Instead, we feed face images into CNN and get a result vector that has a size of 3. Out of 3 in the vector, we can have any number, for example. For simplicity we can say that the first element represents the color of the eye, the second one is the shape of the nose and the third one is the shape of the lips. Now we know that for example, a person's eyes correspond to the color "0" which will be decided by an algorithm which class to assign "0" to (Black for example). As discussed above, the main goal of the CNN is to understand what the main features of the face are and compress it to a much smaller space, so that we can easily calculate afterward who this face belongs to. After using CNN to get the features of the image, now it's time to find similar faces in the database. A database is where face images of all the people who should be recognized are saved. In our case, we can say for example images of family members,

neighbors, or close people. To make it more scalable, all the images from the database are in advance fed in CNN and only feature vectors are saved in the directory, which is very efficient to keep and does not at all take much space. The final phase is to find the detected face from a humanoid robot in the database. The pipeline as discussed previously is as follows: we detect the face; we extract the face and feed it into the CNN to get the features of the face and finally, we compare this feature to all the information in our database to find the corresponding match. There are several ways we can compare feature vectors to each other. We approach this problem as nearest neighbor clustering or nearest neighbor classification problem from machine learning and any statistical algorithm will perform very well if we have good architecture for the CNN. However, in our case, we use C-Support vector classification which is very efficient and performs its calculations in real-time. This is our basic pipeline for Face recognition, but first, we also must talk about how we train CNN to get similar embeddings for similar faces while generating distant embeddings for different faces.

Training - Our main goal for face detection is to have a CNN, that would give us very similar feature embeddings for the same faces while generating different feature embeddings for different faces. To achieve this Face Net uses a triplet loss to train their CNN. Triplet loss means that on each iteration of training the algorithm, they take 3 images. Out of those 3 images, 2 belong to the same person or are very similar while the 3rd one is very different. Now, they train CNN to give very similar embeddings for the 2 faces that look very similar, while generating embeddings for different faces as far away from each other as possible. For simplicity, we can use any measuring step, for example, Euclidean distance. Imagine we have 2 same faces, and we tell our CNN to create embeddings for them where the Euclidean distance between the feature vectors is 0 while keeping in mind to create embeddings for a different image where the distance would be 1. After training for several hours, we would have an algorithm in our hands that can almost perfectly align similar faces and differentiate them from non-similar ones. Hence the name triplet loss comes from the method, where we use triplets to train our algorithm, three images that are fed every iteration. 12

CNN Architecture - As we discussed previously one of the big advantages of the method is that we can use any architecture for face recognition. After several months, many techniques to train CNN were introduced, starting from skip connections to depth-wise convolutional blocks and algorithmically aligned parameters. Recently we also had an outbreak of transformer blocks on image recognition tasks. But as said, we can use any architecture for our case. We can take a state-of-the-art model with the highest efficiency so that it performs in real-time. Retrain it with triplet loss and we will get very high accuracy on face recognition tasks including all the new innovations and additions that were introduced in recent research.

Face Recognition Summary - As we see, the architecture introduced by Face Net stands out in the sense that it's very flexible to changes and performs very well in real-time. We can utilize the power of new research and new deep learning architectures for higher accuracy and more efficiency. Using this algorithm, we are confident to implement a highly accurate face recognition pipeline, with our custom changes in it to make it more robust and efficient for humanoid robot purposes.

**IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF THE TRANSCAUCASIAN CORRIDOR BY
INTRODUCING THE INFRASTRUCTURE OF COMBINED TRANSPORT
LOGISTICS**

Marina Lomidze Assistant professor

Academic Department of Transport and Industry Management, Georgian Technical University, Georgia, 0160, Tbilisi, M. Kostava 68a

Rezo Tedoradze Professor

Academic Department of Road Transport and Logistics, Georgian Technical University, Georgia, 0160, Tbilisi, M. Kostava 68a

Davit Fridonashvili Professor

Academic Department of Road Transport and Logistics, Georgian Technical University, Georgia, 0160, Tbilisi, M. Kostava 68a

Giorgi Sisvadze Assistant professor

Academic Department of Road Transport and Logistics, Georgian Technical University, Georgia, 0160, Tbilisi, M. Kostava 68a

Georgian trunk highway is an important part of the Transcaucasian Corridor, which due to its favorable geographical location makes Georgia not only a logistics hub but also an important Europe-Asia transport route and a corridor linking China-Europe. Consequently, Georgia can get significant economic benefits through the development of transit and logistics infrastructure and technologies. The development of logistics infrastructure and the introduction of new technologies are required to achieve the goal.

65-70% of cargo on Georgian highways are transported by medium and heavy freight road transport, which exhausts gases containing large amounts of harmful substances, which are detrimental to human health, as well as to the surrounding flora and fauna. On Georgian highways this problem can be solved by cooperating two competing types of freight transport - trucks and rail transport chains, when the strengths and advantages of these two transport systems are combined into a single, combined logistics transport system: A railway that efficiently transports goods on long distances as scheduled, without polluting the environment, and a truck that is flexible in transportation and delivers goods from door to door, which also delivers certain cargo flows to the combined transport terminal. (station). Such a solution to the problem is relevant in many developed European countries. By launching the combined freight transport logistics system - road and rail transport, in Georgia, the level of traffic safety on the roads will increase dramatically, freight costs can be reduced on average by 30%, the ecological condition will improve, as air pollution by exhaust gases from the cars will decrease sharply.

The system of combined cargo transportation includes the consolidation of cargo and road transport in terminals (stations), transportation, and distribution from the terminal to the customer. Consequently, the project of this system includes:

1. Study of the characteristic parameters of traffic flows on the Georgian highways and determination of patterns of their variability. Assessment of the traffic modes of vehicles inflows, determination of their characteristics. Modeling of traffic flows and vehicle traffic modes inflows by taking into account real traffic conditions. Development of a method (model) for calculating the amount of environmentally toxic substances that exhaust vehicles. Drawing a distribution diagram of the amount of ecologically harmful substances by the road sections and assessing the ecological condition on the highways.

2. Drawing traffic map of operation of the system, researching and determination of its working parameters, creating the expected technical-economic effects using modern automated systems of management and regulation.

3. Selection of the location of combined railway loading-unloading platforms and terminals (stations), determination and definition of their design parameters, optimization, and harmonization of incoming and outgoing route network with the common route network.

4. Drawing up technical specifications of modern devices and equipment of combined railway loading-unloading platforms and terminals (stations), planning of infrastructure and communication and information infrastructure of the whole system management in accordance with modern international requirements.

INFORMATION SYSTEM OF TELEMEDICINE IN KAZAKHSTAN

Niyazova Zere Temirkhankyzy

Master student at Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Faculty of Information Technologies, Information Systems,

Kubaev Kazila Erekenovich

Doctor of Economic Sciences, Candidate of Technical Sciences, professor at Al-Farabi Kazakh National University

The current state of health care and health care reforms in Kazakhstan sets the task of improving the level and quality of medical care. In the absence of experience of the attending physician, medical consultations or consultations with experienced colleagues are held. However, often an experienced consultant is at a considerable distance from the patient. In the current situation, this problem is solved with the help of telemedicine - remote consultation using telecommunication technologies. It is necessary to develop a telemedicine IS that will automate the process and increase the availability of medical services in Kazakhstan.

The study of the current level of development of telemedicine in the Republic of Kazakhstan and the identification of the main factors of their development.

The information base of the study was normative, reference literature, opinions of various authors in literary sources, and statistical collections. The following methods were used in the study: theoretical, statistical analysis of literary sources, comparative analysis.

Telemedicine is the continuous education of all healthcare professionals, including healthcare professionals, who use information and communication technologies to securely share information for healthcare delivery, diagnosis and treatment, prevention and treatment, disease and injury research and evaluation, to improve people's health. and their communities Telemedicine in Kazakhstan is at an early stage of development. The shortcomings of telemedicine were especially felt during the pandemic, which determined the need for a level of access to medical care and a clear assessment.

One of the problems in the legislative framework is that diagnostics using telemedicine services are not legalized; to start using telemedicine services for consultations, the initial diagnosis must be made directly at the clinic.

This trend makes medicine more and more inaccessible and is based on the fact that medicine in Kazakhstan is used to treat complex or chronic diseases, and not to maintain and improve the health of citizens. Therefore, it is necessary to introduce technologies to prevent the development of the disease and monitor the current state of health.

The following aspects are presented as mechanisms for the growth of telemedicine and teleconsultations:

- Increase in the number of chronic diseases;
- Development of users of smartphones and smart gadgets;
- Technological progress, high Internet access;
- The need to reduce costs in the healthcare system;
- Long waits in hospitals for treatment of illnesses, etc.

There are also limitations and challenges, such as security and privacy issues in telemedicine, and a lack of knowledge and trust in digital health services.

AN ENERGY-EFFICIENT PATH PLANNING FOR UAV

Bayramov Azad Agalar ogli

ScD, professor, Leader Researcher, Institute of Control Systems of Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences

When using UAVs to collect data during terrain monitoring, one of the key tasks is to plan the flight path in such a way as to minimize the power consumption of the UAV. Improving the energy efficiency of UAV is a great practical importance not only for monitoring the terrain. For example, in cases where the UAV is used to search for and rescue trapped people during an earthquake and other places of natural disasters. This can improve the ability of the UAV to fly around as many search and rescue sites as possible, by increasing the flight duration, and save search and rescue time and save more lives.

Currently, most existing methods for planning the optimal path assume the shortest flight distance. This is based on the assumption that the shortest path means the least power consumption of the UAV. However, this ignores the fact that changing direction (course) can also consume UAV power in flight. This is due to the fact that the change in the direction of the velocity vector is achieved due to the acceleration of the UAV, which in turn is associated with an increase in engine thrust, i.e. an increase in energy consumption. This paper proposes a method for energy-efficient UAV trajectory planning. We consider a 3D-space flight and a model the relationship between the angle of change of course and the power consumption of the UAV, and the relationship between the straight-line flight range and the power consumption of the UAV. Then, an energy estimation model is created based on the distance and rotation angle change. Using this model, we can estimate or predict the energy consumption of a UAV to fly from one point in space to another point. This algorithm is used to plan the UAV data collection path according to the estimated energy consumption. The results show that this method can obtain a monitoring flight path with less (up to 10%) power consumption, and a smoother flight path. However, if the number of monitoring points increases to a certain extent, the effect of energy saving planning will decrease. This can be avoided by separating and cooperating multiple UAVs (System of Systems).

НЕТРАДИЦИОННАЯ ВЕТРОВАЯ ЭЛЕКТРОАЭРОДИНАМИЧЕСКАЯ СИСТЕМА

Гелхвидзе Петр Калистратович

Акад. доктор.асоц. Профессор. Кутаисский гос.Университет им.Ак.Церетели, (департамент энергетики и телекоммуникаций), Кутаиси, Грузия.

Keywords: Wind. electric. Energy.

1. Вся история развития человечества тесно связана с вопросом развития энергетических возможностей. Использование электроэнергии на первом месте среди энергетических ресурсов в руках человека сегодня обусловлено удобством ее получения, передачи и использования в различных областях сельского хозяйства и в быту. Никто не сомневается, что увеличение электрических мощностей является главной основой повышения уровня материальной и духовной жизни на пути развития человечества.

Массовое производство электроэнергии в настоящее время основано на использовании гидроэнергетики, преимущественно природного топлива (нефть, газ, уголь, ядерное топливо), что вместе с истощением запасов топлива создает целый комплекс экологических и других проблем. Поэтому одним из приоритетных направлений науки считается поиск эффективных способов использования возобновляемой энергии естественным путем.

2. Примечательно, что атмосфера является одним из уникальных источников энергетических ресурсов Земли. Ветер является одним из его ресурсом, энергия которого достаточно велика. Электричество, вырабатываемое человечеством на сегодняшний день, в основном основано на законе электромагнитной индукции, для чего необходимо использовать некую систему (ротор) и за счет неэлектрической энергии вырабатывать электрическую энергию.

3. Все известные в настоящее время генераторы, работающие на энергии ветра, работают на основе упомянутого выше закона, т.е. магнитная система, вращающаяся за счет механической энергии ветра. Кроме того, в этих установках используется множество дополнительных устройств, таких как регуляторы, тормоза, мультипликаторы и др. Это усложняет конструкцию установки, вызывает дополнительные потери энергии, сокращает продолжительность эксплуатации и увеличивает нежелательные затраты. Все это препятствует широкому использованию энергии ветра, поэтому в настоящее время его вклад нетрадиционной энергетике, в общий энергетический баланс очень мал.

Следовательно, проблема эффективного использования энергии ветра весьма актуальна и требует скорейшего решения.

4. Эти вопросы в настоящее время исследуются во всем мире, выдаются патенты на устройства, но большинство из них посвящено совершенствованию существующих методов и совершенствованию традиционных машин, при этом результатов становится все меньше, поскольку традиционные методы исчерпали свои возможности развития и по существу необходимы, для перейти на качественно новый этап, разработать новые методы!

5. Предлагаемый способ будет использовать способ получения электрического тока из ионных потоков, генерируемых электризацией на основе взаимодействия горячего и холодного вихревых потоков воздуха. Известно, что так называемое устройство «Ranke Tube» (патент США № 1952281), обеспечивающий разделение газа на горячие и холодные потоки. Этот эффект многократно доказан экспериментально,

но его физическая сущность до конца не изучена, и отсутствуют научные исследования, использующие этот эффект для получения электрического тока.

В работе, предложен использовать ряд физических эффектов (различные способы ионизации газовых потоков, обратный эффект электроосмоса, трибоэлектрический эффект и др.), обеспечивающих преобразование энергии газового потока в электрическую без промежуточных систем.

Вывод: Все вышеизложенное является основой для разработки метода преобразования энергии ветра в электрическую энергию и проектированию модели электро аэродинамического генератора без каких-либо промежуточных и подвижных систем, (и без использования закона электромагнитной индукции Фарадея).

Предложеный нетрадиционный способ преобразования энергии ветра в электрическую и модель электро аэродинамического генератора, которая будет конструктивно проста, высокоэффективна и экологически безопасна, придадут исследованию новизну и уникальность.

FEATURES OF THE FUNCTIONING OF THE INTEGRATED MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN A PUBLIC TRANSPORT ENTERPRISE

Yegdirov Nurlan Tileukabakovich

Master's student, L.N.Gumilyov Eurasian National University, Nur-Sultan, Kazakhstan

Kirghizbaeva Kamila Zhuzbayevna

Candidate of Technical Sciences, Docent, L.N.Gumilyov Eurasian National University, Nur-Sultan, Kazakhstan

Annotation: Public transport is a basic element in human life. For effective management of the process of passenger transportation, complete information about the level of service of the transport company is required. This will allow the adoption of managerial decisions on the organization of transport services for the population based on the real ability of carriers to provide a given level of quality of transportation. Every year, a certain number of problems are noticed that require solutions. The introduction of integrated management systems is one of the elements for solving these problems in the course of a scientific article.

Keywords: Integrated management system, public transport, enterprise management, passenger, consumer, quality

Introduction: In 2021, the population of Kazakhstan reached 19 million people, of which more than 10 million people are urban residents. A high degree of urbanization describes the importance of urban and suburban public transport in the life of the country. Realizing their needs for movement, the population of the country makes more than 500 trips per inhabitant every year, taking into account all ages.

In the modern world, public transport enterprises, in order to improve the operation of the enterprise, are acutely concerned with such issues as monitoring vehicles, monitoring passenger flows, managing urban and suburban passenger transportation.

In Kazakhstan, obsolete buses are observed in moral and technical terms. It is possible to notice the admitted problems on the part of transport companies providing the service of transportation of passengers. These are problems with the route of buses, waiting for a bus longer than the allotted time, the lack of qualified specialists capable of designing and managing urban transport systems.

Moreover, based on the comments and complaints left, we can draw the following conclusions: lack of a comfortable ride in compliance with traffic rules, low speed of movement, the flow of vehicles at rush hour, little attention to bus lines, outdated buses with high costs in the form of emissions of harmful substances in environment, etc.

Kazakhstan has a number of public transport regulations and laws that serve as guidelines and planning basis for the necessary procedures. The government takes a centralized approach to management and lawmaking procedures, not only providing a general strategic approach to transport-related issues, but also defining specific technical and safety standards.

Method: The use of new methods and technologies in transport enterprises to manage transportation activities is a hot topic, since the volume of traffic is growing every year, the amount of transportation costs is increasing, and the need to improve the quality of services provided is increasing.

The existing methods of management lead the industry to the fact that after some time, if the right conclusions are not made, there will be a complete loss of control of the passenger transportation industry. In conditions when the main problem of carriers is the lack of financial resources, the need for their rational use is of particular importance.

However, it is obvious that at the present stage, many tasks cannot be solved without the introduction of new methods and technologies, one of which is the introduction of an integrated management system in a public transport enterprise.

The main task of the IMS for such a management system is to provide quality service, quality passenger service, ensuring safety and saving the resources of transport enterprises.

The basis: IMS allows you to increase the efficiency of the entire enterprise management system as a whole through a comprehensive solution of the problems of organizational, economic, technological and environmental management, which allows you to take into account the existing relationships and interdependencies between them and obtain a synergistic effect from their joint solution. Based on the foregoing, it can be concluded that the introduction of IMS at domestic enterprises in Kazakhstan will be the basis for their successful transition to sustainable development in modern conditions.

A well-implemented IMS ensures greater coordination of actions within the organization, thereby enhancing the synergistic effect, which means that the overall result from coordinated actions is higher than the simple sum of individual results:

- the introduction of IMS allows to increase the competitiveness of the enterprise by increasing the level of its business reputation and improving the quality of organization management;

- IMS minimizes the functional disunity of personnel in the organization that occurs during the development of autonomous management systems;

- the creation of an integrated system, as a rule, is much less laborious than the creation of several parallel systems. The costs of developing, operating and certifying an integrated system are lower than the total costs of several management systems;

- IMS allows you to better balance the interests of the external parties of the organization than in the presence of parallel functioning systems;

- Achievement of greater "transparency" and manageability, as the number of internal and external links in an integrated system is less than the total number of these links in several systems;

- the volume of documents in the integrated system is significantly reduced compared to the total volume of documents in several parallel systems. In an integrated system, a higher degree of personnel involvement in improving the organization's activities is achieved;

- the effectiveness of the integrated management system is increased through the use of joint activities in the integrated system, such as policy setting, planning, staff training, etc.;

- integration also helps to reduce conflicts and the likelihood of possible contradictions between issues related to quality, ecology and safety, a more holistic approach to increasing profitability, more efficient use of resources, improving the coherence of the information exchange process, eliminating duplication of processes.

It should be emphasized that the integration of management systems is carried out primarily to obtain benefits in accordance with the needs of the enterprise to optimize its internal environment, which must be obtained while meeting the requirements of international standards.

With this approach to the integration of management systems, it is advisable to make a decision to create an integrated management system, based on the current state of the enterprise management system, based on identifying and analyzing the problems in it, the possibilities for solving them, and achieving the necessary improvements, taking into account the possible benefits of integration. .

Analysis and other tools can be used to identify problems to be solved by integration.

In general, the meaning of creating an integrated management system is at least to ensure purposeful activity and consistency of decisions made and established goals for

individual management systems, as well as avoiding duplication of actions, responsibility, data registration, etc., improving the exchange of information between employees, departments and with interested parties, including contractors.

Conclusion: The creation of IMS at enterprises will eliminate the duplication of processes, documents, positions and functions in the organization's divisions; speed up the process of implementing a group of standards in the enterprise. In addition, as world experience shows, an effective environmental management system in modern conditions cannot be created without the effective functioning of IMS at an enterprise.

Thus, when forming an IMS at enterprises in Kazakhstan, it will help to avoid erroneous management decisions and increase the efficiency of integration of management systems, which, in turn, systematizes the entire process of managing an enterprise as a whole and increases its competitiveness in conditions of unstable external environment and increasing competition.

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ВОПРОСЫ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ В АГРАРНОМ СЕКТОРЕ КАЗАХСТАНА

Калдыбаева Данира Орынбаевна

Докторант 2-го курса Евразийского Национального Университета им.Л.Н.Гумилева, РК

Пандемия коронавируса, резкое ухудшение политической ситуации в мире привело к сильным экономическим и финансовым потрясениям. Сильное повышение цен на энергоносители в мире привели к неудержимому росту цен на все жизненно важные продукты, в том числе и на продовольственные. Эти факторы стали причиной резкого повышения актуальности решения вопросов продовольственной безопасности всех государств. Это, в свою очередь, повысило значимость проблемы повышения эффективности аграрного сектора, как основного источника продовольственного сырья.

Казахстан является страной с аграрной экономикой, но, при этом его доля в общем ВВП страны составляет не более чем 5-10 %. Обладая огромным сельскохозяйственным потенциалом, данная отрасль сильно отстает в технологическом и техническом плане от других секторов экономики. Особенно, это заметно на фоне стремительного развития цифровых технологий практически во всех прочих отраслях деятельности человечества. Несмотря на появление множества современных способов и средств, созданных на основе цифровых методов, сельхозпроизводители в Казахстане на данный момент очень пассивно внедряют их в производственную деятельность. Согласно статистическим исследованиям данные цифровые технологии используют лишь 2-5 % сельскохозяйственных товаропроизводителей и доля затрат на эти инновации не превышают и одного процента совокупных затрат хозяйств.

Однако, за последние годы общее отношение к данным новинкам изменилось в положительную сторону. И сегодня, когда идёт речь о цифровых решениях, это уже не вызывает резкое отрицание. Предприниматели стали понимать, что данные цифровые методы являются очень сильным средством повышения эффективности производства. При этом, рассматривая экономическую эффективность как отношение полученных результатов (доходов) к потребленным ресурсам (трудовым, материальным, финансовым и др.), надо понимать, что цифровые методы достаточно значимо воздействуют как на числитель, так и на знаменатель данной формулы, т.е. современные цифровые технологии ощутимо повышая продуктивность и урожайность хозяйств, также достаточно сильно дают возможность получать экономию на затратах, за счет сокращения удельных затрат топлива, семян, химпрепаратов, живого труда и т.д.

Таким образом, можно констатировать, что цифровизация нашла путь в аграрный сектор страны. Это можно видеть по появлению новых современных цифровых платформ, например Qoldau, «ИнтТерра» и др. Конечно, наша страна находится еще в начале пути, но в целом наблюдается положительная тенденция в этом вопросе. Несомненным является лишь факт, что цифровая трансформация сельского хозяйства страны станет мощным направлением повышения эффективности сельскохозяйственной отрасли и обеспечит ее устойчивое развитие в будущем.

WASTE HEAT RECOVERY: USE IN GREENHOUSES

Baikatov Taimas Timurovich

Master Degree Student, Heat Power Engineering, Almaty University of Power Engineering and Telecommunications named after G. Daukeev

According to the statistical reports by the Agency of Statistics of Kazakhstan, the total annual emissions of pollutants into the atmosphere in Almaty in 2021 amounted to 69,500 tons, including emissions from thermal power plants and industrial plants, of which 11,700 tons per year are from the CHP-1 (Combined Heat & Power). And while there are constant improvements to reduce the air pollution in recent years, Almaty still occupies leading positions among the most polluted cities in Kazakhstan.

Combustion of solid fuel in boilers at thermal-fueled power plants (CHPs) generates large amounts of sulfur dioxide, nitric oxide and particulate matter (ash), which pollute and have a negative impact on the environment. From fossil fuels natural gas represents the best alternative to solid fuel in terms of its higher fuel efficiency and much lower emissions.

In recent years, much attention is being paid to the development and use of energy saving technologies that make efficient use of the waste heat from combustion products, thereby reducing harmful emissions. One of the possible options is uses of greenhouses. To effectively collect and use the heat form the autonomic heating systems installed in buildings (with its own autonomic boiler, fueled with natural gas), greenhouses can be allocated on the roofs residential, office facilities. This will allow to recover waste heat of multi-story buildings for heating of greenhouses and enriching plants its plants with carbon dioxide to increase productivity in the cold seasons.

Taken into account changes in CO₂ demand throughout the day by the plants and maximum permissible concentrations of carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and sulfur dioxide (SO₂) the maximum yield is achieved, without causing damage to the plants.

To increase the crop yield of greenhouse the exhaust gas is supplied to its upper part via pipe with holes, which does not require any operating personnel and is regulated with equipment on the greenhouse entrance. The total estimated expenses, for purchasing equipment and materials for the greenhouse is much less than energy saved.

Thus, the use of waste heat of exhaust gases from autonomic CHP boiler for heating greenhouses provides the following: saving energy, enhancing plant growth due to enrichment in carbon dioxide and reducing emissions of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere.

APPLICATION OF GEOGRAPHICAL INFORMATION SYSTEM IN SOCIO-ECONOMIC GEOGRAPHY IN KAZAKHSTAN

Zharmagambetova A.Zh.,

MSc at Al-Farabi Kazakh National University

In the world of digitalization, Geographical Information Systems (GIS) can be applied and connected in a wide range of realms, which people mostly do not tend to think about, for instance, medicine, aviation, film industry, animation, gaming, banking, media, etc. In many developing countries, the role of GIS for centralized planning, management, and decision-making is continuing to increase in importance because of growing pressures from overpopulation, depletion of natural resources, and financial instability. Therefore, GIS is one of the developing domains over the last decades. One of the fields, where geographical information systems are widely recognized is social-economic geography including demography, urbanization, public health, etc.

Geographical Information Systems play a major role in health care, surveillance of infectious diseases, and mapping and monitoring of spatial and temporal distributions of vectors of infections. GIS combine complex algorithms, spatial analysis, geo-statistics, and modeling, which makes geospatial technologies a powerful tool for predicting the nature of diseases and ecological associations of parasites (Zhuspekova, Maymurunova, 2015). The integration of public health and GIS is an active research area. While digitalizing results and statistics using GIS tools, there will be some challenges. However, many challenges are still to be solved.

There are few challenges as data availability, technical capacity, and access to GIS infrastructure, at the usage of GIS tools in Kazakhstan, and the discussion of strategies that can be

used to overcome some of these problems and future work, which could be done for the enhancement of this field.

The five components of GIS are data, hardware, software, procedures, people. Public health data is ideal for processing and analyzing as information layers in GIS. Additional information layers, for example, census data or environmental data can be added to the database and requested along with health data map, analyze, interpret, and simulate the spread of disease and disease. If one or more GIS components are missing or insufficiently provided with resources, the Geospatial database loses its analytical and predictive capabilities. Problems occur when data is collected unevenly or when the layers of information are collected in the absence of appropriate procedures for processing and storing data, as well as in the presence of appropriate equipment and software access is limited. In the fight against zoonotic diseases, such as rabies, brucellosis, and echinococcosis, which mainly affect developing countries, these problems are barriers to creating effective and efficient GIS architectures (Fletcher, Caprareli, 2016).

In conclusion, I would like to note that GIS technologies are actively used in various countries but in most of the studied use of technology involves more than the creation of interactive maps with information visualization facilities and other capabilities that are listed in the studied projects. However, while technology has not been as widespread in the world, let's hope for the emergence of the development of new technologies in this sphere and modern methods of providing the necessary information.

ПРЕДОТВРАЩЕНИЕ ПОТЕРИ РАБОЧЕЙ ЖИДКОСТИ В ОПРЫСКИВАТЕЛЯХ

Багиров Байрам Мухаммад оглы

д.т.н., профессор, Азербайджанский Технологический Университет.

Мамедов Зия Виляет оглы

ассистент, Азербайджанский Государственный Аграрный Университет

Для защиты растений от болезней, вредителей и сорняков в настоящее время наиболее широко применяются наземные опрыскиватели. Для опрыскивания этими машинами рабочую жидкость готовят путем смешивания пестицидных препаратов с водой. Полученная рабочая жидкость распыляется на растения под давлением. В зависимости от количества наносимого вещества и размера капель: крупные, средние, мелкие, и мельчайшие капли распыление производится опрыскивания растений, в поле. В последнее время для опрыскивания растений у нас в республике, в основном используют штанговые опрыскиватели. Это связано с тем, что штанговые опрыскиватели рабочей жидкостью распыляются непосредственно на растения, с близкого расстояния, что положительно сказывается на эффективности работы.

В результате исследований установлено, что в каждой смене рабочего дня, после каждой остановки насоса (при остановки или холостых ходах агрегата и при поворотных полосах на обоих концах поля) при опрыскивании рабочая жидкость, оставшаяся в коммуникационных линиях – в шлангах и трубопроводах от распределителя до опрыскивающих форсунок – из-за разницы уровней штанги или вибрации штанги опрыскивающего агрегата по полю, от центробежные или в поворотной полосе, из форсунок опрыскивателя протекает рабочая жидкость, что вызывает потери рабочей жидкости, также и потерю в ней пестицидов. Это снижает производительность опрыскивающего агрегата и негативно влияет на окружающую среду. Поэтому исследование и разработка методы и средства для предотвращения этих потерь рабочей жидкости опрыскивателях является актуально.

Учитывая актуальность указанного вопроса, нами разработан и применен обратный клапан, который устанавливается внутри каждой форсунки опрыскивателя. Это предотвращает свободного вытекание рабочей жидкости из распылительных форсунок, во всех случаях остановки насоса опрыскивателя.

Результаты исследований был внедрен в производства при опрыскивание растение хлопчатника. Установлен что от внедрения обратного клапана в каждом форсунке опрыскивателя экономия средств в год. на единицу опрыскивающего агрегата составляе более чем 2000 манатов.

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ РАБОТЫ ВЕРТИКАЛЬНОГО СМЕСИТЕЛЯ КОРМОВ ПЕРИОДИЧЕСКОГО ДЕЙСТВИЕ

Агаев Эмил Фикрат оглы

Азербайджанский Научно - Исследовательский Институт "Агро механика"

Багиров Байрам Мухаммад оглы, д.т.н., профессор

Азербайджанский Технологический Университет.

Наукой и практикой доказана, что кормление животных полнорационными корм смесями позволяет повысить продуктивность кормов на 5...9%, увеличить привеса молодняка крупного рогатого скота на 11...20% в сравнении с отдельным скормливанием кормовых компонентов. При этом экономится до 10...15% кормов. Наибольшее распространение получило приготовление рассыпных корм смесей. Анализ научно – исследовательских работ в области техники и технологии приготовления, полнорационных корм смесей показал преимущество применения кормосмесителей периодического действия. Это связано с тем, что ввиду циркуляции в смесителе кормовых компонентов достигается кормовые смеси высокого качества. Вместе с тем остается ещё актуальным вопрос исследования и выбора рациональных параметров и совершенствование технических средств по этому направлению с учётом экономии энергии и ресурсных затрат.

Животноводство является основным потребителем кормов, однако, поскольку ни один вид корма не содержит полного набора необходимых для животных питательных веществ, витаминов и микроэлементов, они плохо развиваются при скормливании отдельного вида корма. У них снижается продуктивность, увеличивается расход кормов на единицу продукции и в конечном итоге снижается рентабельность производства. В результате расход кормов на 1 ц молока превышает затраты труда в 1,5 раза, производство говядины в 2,5 раза, производство мяса птицы в 1,3 раза. Только качественная кормовая смесь обеспечивает животное необходимым количеством и пропорцией питательных веществ, что способствует повышению их продуктивности на 15...20 %

Твердые комбикорма в кормовом рационе крупного рогатого скота составляют 35 %, а в кормовом рационе птицы 90...95 %. Сильные комбикорма готовят на специальных предприятиях и специализированных комбикормовых заводах. Следует отметить, что такие существующие предприятия не в полной мере обеспечивают потребности скота в этих кормах. При этом следует отметить, что значительная часть затрат приходится на транспортировку сырья и готовой продукции. Зачастую комбикорма, приготовленные комбикормовыми заводами, не соответствуют требуемым показателям качества. По данным научных организаций, только 2% из многочисленных проб продукции различных комбикормовых заводов, занятых производством этих кормов, соответствовали норме.

Стоимость используемых ингредиентов играет важную роль в стоимости корма. Поэтому приготовление кормов должно максимально основываться на сырье, производимом в хозяйстве (зерновые и масличные культуры, белковые компоненты, минеральные компоненты). В связи с этим для эффективного использования его сырья необходимо сбалансировать приготовленный корм обогащающими добавками, например, полиферментными композициями (ферментами). Важно иметь возможности контроля качества в ходе технологических операций по приготовлению сбалансированной кормосмеси.

Нами проведены работы по совершенствованию конструкции вертикального кормосмесителя периодического типа для устранения случаев задержки выгрузки готовой смеси. Так как это отрицательно влияет на производительность и рядом с ней энергетических, трудовых и материальных затрат. Рассматривали задачи, связанные с технологической, цикловой среднечасовой производительностью. Произведен анализ влияния емкости смесителя на его производительность, выраженный специальным коэффициентом. Определены пределы этого коэффициента, который характеризует производительность установки. Установлено, что при правильной эксплуатации производительности, вертикального кормосмесителя периодического типа в основном обеспечивается количеством циклов шнека, периодической принудительной подачи смеси - а качество перемешивания, угла наклона ребер шнека в конструкции машин.

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**NUMERICAL MODELING OF INTERACTION BETWEEN PILES AND
SUBSIDING FOUNDATION SOIL**

S.Nyamdorj

Mongolian State University of Science and Technology. School of Civil Engineering.
Ulaanbaamar. Mongolia

D.Oyungerel

Mongolian State University of Science and Technology. School of Civil Engineering.
Ulaanbaamar. Mongolia

Introduction. Numerical modeling using the finite element method makes it possible to solve the problem of the features of building and construction work, including the base and foundation in complex engineering and geological conditions, taking into account the regional features of the study area, at a relatively low cost. Currently, SCAD office, Lira, Robot Structural Analysis, Plaxis, Ansys, Abaqus and other computational software systems are widely used to solve geotechnical problems. Of these, Plaxis 2D and 3D software package was developed in accordance with the guidelines of EUROCODE-7, which regulates the issues of engineering calculations and design of the base, foundation and geotechnical objects. Along with this, the Government of Mongolia has decided to base the regulatory documents for the design of civil and engineering structures on the main provisions of EUROCODE, so the issue of studying and competent possession of Plaxis is important.

I. Rationale for application. Dalerci G., Del Grosso A. (1981), Schanz T., Vermeer P.A., Bonnier P.G. (1999), Frank R. (2004; 2006), Basu D. and Salgado R. (2009), Mangushev R.A. (2010), Vlasov A.N. (2012), Fadeev A.B. (2012), Kolyaskina S. A. (2014) and others developed a numerical modeling technique using the finite element method and investigated the problem of the reasonable use of the Plaxis 2D and 3D software package. The main elements of the numerical simulation of the Plaxis program are the fourth-order interpolation elements with 15 nodes. In such elements, the displacement at all 15 nodes, the stress at 12 points are determined by the results of solving refined integrations. The sides of such finite elements can be straight lines and curves. If the side is curvilinear, then enter one point at the midpoint, this method performs modeling. Such a high-order polynomial is limited by the total number of nodes (in our case, 15 nodes), as a result of the latter, by comparing lower order polynomials, it is possible to obtain more accurate calculation results in the end. At the modern level of development of numerical modeling in spatial representation, there is no single methodology for the calculation model for the joint operation of the “building and foundation soil” system of structures, based on this circumstance, the problem of optimal choice remains important and open.

II. Analysis of results. In order to identify the features of the joint operation of a bored pile and a pre-soaked subsiding soil of the base, numerical modeling was carried out using the finite element method and the calculation of the bearing capacity and settlement using the Plaxis 2D program. Calculation parameters for modeling: reinforced concrete pile, operating in a hard mode according to the principle of the Mohr-Coulomb law, with a length of 8.0 m and a diameter of 0.6 m, base soil loesslike subsiding sandy loam, soaked to water saturation according to the state of moisture and the relevant physical and mechanical characteristics of reinforced concrete and soils.

Conclusion. Compared to the results of numerical solutions and field tests, it is about 3.0%, that is, under the action of the maximum horizontal load (150 kN), the average numerical value of the horizontal displacement is 38.164 mm, and then according to the numerical solution 39.00 mm. From this, it is possible to draw conclusions that the solution

based on numerical simulation gives results with high accuracy compared to the results of field tests.

Health & Medical Science

- Addiction
- AIDS & HIV
- Alternative & Traditional Medicine
- Anesthesiology
- Audiology, Speech & Language Pathology
- Bioethics
- Biomedical Technology
- Cardiology
- Child & Adolescent Psychology
- Clinical Laboratory Science
- Communicable Diseases
- Critical Care
- Dentistry
- Dermatology
- Developmental Disabilities
- Diabetes
- Emergency Medicine
- Endocrinology
- Epidemiology
- Gastroenterology & Hepatology
- Genetics & Genomics
- Gerontology & Geriatric Medicine
- Gynecology & Obstetrics
- Health & Medical Sciences (general)
- Heart & Thoracic Surgery
- Hematology
- Hospice & Palliative Care
- Immunology
- Medical Informatics
- Medicinal Chemistry
- Molecular Biology
- Natural Medicines & Medicinal Plants
- Neurology
- Neurosurgery
- Nuclear Medicine, Radiotherapy & Molecular Imaging
- Nursing
- Nutrition Science
- Obesity
- Oncology
- Ophthalmology & Optometry
- Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery
- Orthopedic Medicine & Surgery
- Otolaryngology
- Pain & Pain Management
- Pathology
- Pediatric Medicine
- Pharmacology & Pharmacy
- Physical Education & Sports Medicine
- Physiology
- Pregnancy & Childbirth
- Primary Health Care
- Psychiatry
- Psychology
- Public Health
- Pulmonology
- Radiology & Medical Imaging
- Rehabilitation Therapy
- Reproductive Health
- Rheumatology
- Social Psychology
- Surgery
- Toxicology
- Transplantation
- Tropical Medicine & Parasitology
- Urology & Nephrology
- Vascular Medicine
- Veterinary Medicine
- Virology
- Plastic & Reconstructive Surgery

**SELECTION OF STAPHYLOCOCCAL IMMUNOGENS AND DEVELOPMENT OF
POLYCLONAL IMMUNOGLOBULIN**

Rigvava Sergo

George Eliava Institute of Bacteriophages, Microbiology and Virology

Gubeladze Lia

George Eliava Institute of Bacteriophages, Microbiology and Virology

Natidze Merab

George Eliava Institute of Bacteriophages, Microbiology and Virology

Gogiashvili Dali

George Eliava Institute of Bacteriophages, Microbiology and Virology

Dalakishvili Tamar

George Eliava Institute of Bacteriophages, Microbiology and Virology

Kavtaradze Lali

George Eliava Institute of Bacteriophages, Microbiology and Virology

Aim of the study is the selection of staphylococci and pathogenic factors synthesized by them, preparation of immunogens, immunization of producer-animals (goat), fractionation of isolated immune serum, investigation of the obtained immunoglobulin. The purpose of immunoglobulin is to treat complicated staphylococcal infections in humans and animals. Our studies are based on hoarse anti-staphylococcal immunoglobulin obtained in G. Eliava Institute in 1985, which contained only antibacterial and antitoxic (a-toxin) antibodies. According to the data from Sepsis Center, immunoglobulin was used in more than 300 patients with severe staphylococcal sepsis, antibiotics and other medicinal agents did not produce the desired result for them. 88% of patients were completely cured as a result of using immunoglobulin.

30 strains with stable characteristics (Staphyl.aureus-24, Staphyl. epidermidis-6) have been selected from 102 laboratory and clinical cultures of staphylococci. Morphological, cultural and enzymatic activity of strains, susceptibility to novobiocin and staphylococcal bacteriophage, ability to form microcapsule, proteolytic, hemolytic, mannitol fermentation and plasmocoagulation values have been studied using prepared immunogens (thermally inactivated staphylococcal culture – 5 bln/ml; alpha-anatoxin, PV-leukocidin). Producer-animals were immunized according to the schedule. In addition to the above-mentioned immunogens, chromatographically purified bacterial hyaluronidase (Staphylococcus aureus-O-15) was used for immunization. It is known, that it can damage connective tissue of the body and cause development of inflammatory processes. Immunogens were administered in increasing doses - thermally-inactivated culture of staphylococci (5 billion/ml) - 0.5 ml; Second vaccine - 1 ml; Third vaccine - 2 ml; Fourth vaccine - 4.0 ml; Adsorbed staphylococcal anatoxin - first vaccine - 1 ml, second - 2 ml, third - 3.5 ml, fourth vaccine - 4.5 ml. PV-leukocidin - first injection - 0.1 mg, second injection - 0.2 mg, third injection - 0.4 mg. These injections coincide in time with the second, third and fourth injections of anatoxin. Hyaluronidase - 0.2 mg first injection, 0.4 mg second injection. Immunogens were supplemented with 0,5% adjuvant ($KAl(SO_4)_2$). Anti-staphylococcal polyclonal immunoglobulin was obtained by serum (7200 ml) alcohol fractionation (Chon et al.). Specific antibodies to bacteria, toxins (alpha-toxin, PV-leukocidin) and enzyme (hyaluronidase) were studied. Titer of antitoxic antibodies in the Limes-hemolysis (Lh) reaction was 150 IU/ml in contrast to the standard serum. To evaluate antibodies against

immunogens, we developed diagnostic test-system, which was used in passive (indirect) hemagglutination reaction (PHA). Titer of antibacterial antibodies in PHA was 1:6400 - 1:12800, and the titer of anti-leukocidin antibodies was: 1:640 - 1: 1280; The titer of antibodies to hyaluronidase in PHA was 1:320 - 1:640. Normal goat serum and immunoglobulin were studied by immunoenzyme method. Results were registered on reader Sunostik SPR-960. To perform immunoenzyme analysis, we used the following reagent: Anti-Goat IgG (H&L) in rabbit Affinity Purified, Polysciences, Inc. exp. 10.2022). According to the normal values 50-390 ng/ml immunoenzyme analysis has been performed, generally based on "Sandwich-ELISA". Average data for normal (control) serums against staphylococcal toxin were 0,081; and positivity index of immunoglobulin against the same toxin was 10,08, positivity index of antibacterial antibodies - 2,3287, positivity index of PV leukocidin-4,3968, and of hyaluronidase -0,9214. Immunoglobulin, which was studied according to the requirements of European Pharmacopoeia in the experiment in white mice and guinea pigs, was revealed to be sterile, non-toxic, harmless (non-reactive), non-pyrogenic. Study of therapeutic properties revealed that anti-staphylococcal immunoglobulin protects white mice from DC (unconditionally lethal dose of bacterium and toxin) by 90-92%, while 100% of animals from control group died within 24 hours. Next step in the project is obtaining of antibody fragments F(ab') and their immunochemical, biochemical, serological and in vitro study.

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**THE IMPACT OF PSYCHOGENIC FACTORS ON THE MILD COGNITIVE
IMPAIRMENTS IN THE ELDERLY PATIENTS**

Madina Kassymzhanova

S.D. Asfendiyarov Kazakh National Medical University, Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan

Natalya Raspopova

S.D. Asfendiyarov Kazakh National Medical University, Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan

Abstract

Background. Individuals with particular qualities or characteristics are predisposed to develop cognitive impairment non dementia. We aimed to study socio-demographic factors and personality traits, that contribute to the development of depressive disorders in elderly patients with cognitive deficits.

Keywords: elderly; mild cognitive impairment; anxiety; depression; dementia

Materials and methods. We conducted an observational study involving 111 patients from Kazakhstan with cognitive deficits: 59 patients, whose depressive disorders had been identified by clinical and psychopathological research using the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale and 52 patients for whom psychogenic depressive disorders had not been defined. We used the Pearson's chi-squared test and the odds ratio (OR) to quantify the relationship between depression and the predictors under study.

Results. We revealed an association between depression and sex ($p = 0.001$), marital status ($p \leq 0.001$), and the nature of the patients' relationship with relatives ($p = 0.005$) was revealed. Further, we found that the chance of developing depression was higher in female patients (OR = 3.657), lonely patients (OR = 5.984), and patients with conflicting relationships with relatives (OR = 3.222). The frequency of depression was higher in patients with the personality traits of isolation (OR = 2.624, $p = 0.016$), insecurity (OR = 2.879, $p = 0.007$), and passivity (OR = 2.175, $p = 0.049$). Patients showing the "stuckness" effect (OR = 2.924, $p = 0.049$), pathological properties of dysthymia (OR = 2.279, $p = 0.035$), and anxiety (OR = 4.345, $p = 0.001$), were more likely to develop depression.

Conclusion. The likelihood of patients with cognitive deficits developing a depressive disorder is influenced by the patients' personal characteristics (gender, marital status, and the nature of the patients' relationship with relatives), premorbid personality patterns (isolation, insecurity, and passivity), and the pathological personality properties of stuckness, dysthymia, and anxiety.

In the group with complex therapy, where the therapy was carried out with anti-dementia treatment and psycho-pharmacotherapy plus psycho-correction, better results in cognitive abilities were recorded than in the group with only anti-dementia therapy. It was found that anxiety-depressive disorders in the elderly can significantly affect the depth, severity and dynamics of vascular cognitive impairments, and their timely detection and targeted treatment can significantly increase the effectiveness of anti-dementia therapy and suspend/delay further decline in cognitive functions.

IMPACT OF CYP3A5 GENE POLYMORPHISM ON TACROLIMUS PHARMACOKINETICS IN KIDNEY TRANSPLANT PATIENTS IN KAZAKH POPULATION

Madadov Islam Kurbanovich

MD, urologist, transplant surgeon, junior researcher, National Scientific Center of surgery named after A.N.Syzganov

Kidney transplantation nowadays is the best therapeutic option for end-stage kidney disease. Kidney transplantation is the most preferable treatment option of terminal chronic kidney disease. The main advantage of kidney transplantation is that graft totally replaces the function of diseased kidney. Improvement of the quality of life of patients and return to their daily activities is another great advantage of this option.

With the improvement of donor selection, surgical technique and rational immunosuppressive treatment rates of short-term graft survival great increased. 1 –year graft survival from deceased donor is 95% whereas from living related donor is 98%. In Kazakhstan 1-year graft survival from living related donor is 91%. Despite these high indicators of 1-year graft survival, 5-year graft survival rates remain to be low. For example, in USA 5-year graft survival from deceased donor is up to 80%, whereas from living donor is from 82 to 90 %, respectively. Thus, despite the improvement of short-term graft survival rates, long-term graft survival rates remain to be low.

So what lies under the graft loss in long-term period? It is thought to be that the main reason of graft loss in long-term period is so called graft nephropathy. The reasons of graft nephropathy are immunologic factors and, probably, genetic factors.

Recently there are many transplant centers where genetic factors and their influence of kidney graft function are investigated. In this way investigation of CYP3A5 genetic polymorphism, as a regulatory factor of tacrolimus pharmacokinetics is being more relevant.

We conducted a clinical trial, where we include 80 kidney recipients. Of them, 47 were male and 33 female patients. Mean age of patients was 43 ± 4.1 years. All patients had been taking tacrolimus 0.1 mg/kg initially. Dose adjustment was by 1.0 mg a day up to target concentration (10-12 ng/ml). All patients were studied for CYP3A5 genetic polymorphism.

According to the results in our study 61.25% (n=49) of patients were homozygotes, CYP3A5*3*3 carriers (non-expressers) and 38.75% (n=31) were heterozygotes, CYP3A5*1*3 carriers (with one expressor allele). Patients were arranged by sex/type of polymorphism by Fisher's test. There were no significant differences in sex/CYP3A5 genetic polymorphism in patients. Patients were divided into 2 groups: homozygotes and heterozygotes. Tacrolimus concentration was measured on 2, 5th, 7th, 10th and 14th days after surgery and at discharge. There were significant differences in concentrations on 2nd, 5th, 7th and 10th days in both groups ($p = 0.02, 0.01, 0.12$ and 0.016 , respectively). There were no significant statistical differences in tacrolimus concentration on 14 day after the surgery and at discharge ($p = 0.085$ and 0.171 , respectively). In both groups tacrolimus almost reached target level at the end of 2nd week, but in heterozygotes increase was more gradual and predictable rather than in homozygotes. There were no substantial differences in graft function. Creatinine level normalized gradually in both groups and there were not significant differences in both groups at discharge

It is obvious from received results, that genetic polymorphism of CYP3A5 influences tacrolimus blood concentration, that appears to be key factor in immunosuppression. Even in rational choice of dose of immunosuppressive agent, genetic factor must be considered as well. In order to improve long-term graft survival rates it is important to maintain therapeutic

concentration of tacrolimus in blood. In this way it might be important to determine the CYP3A5 genetic polymorphism preoperatively, as one of the approved genetic determinants of graft survival. It is also important for the correct selection of initial dose.

**EPIDEMIOLOGICAL AND CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF
HEPATOCELLULAR CARCINOMA IN KAZAKHSTAN**

Aikerim Saktagan

Department of Gastroenterology, Asfendiyarov National Medical University, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Zuhra Agzamova

Department of Gastroenterology, Asfendiyarov National Medical University, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Arailym Maikenova

Department of Gastroenterology, Asfendiyarov National Medical University, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Kamila Zhumagalieva

Department of Gastroenterology, Asfendiyarov National Medical University, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Alexander V. Nersesov.

Department of Gastroenterology, Asfendiyarov National Medical University, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Гепатоцеллюлярная карцинома печени (ГЦК) является одной из частых причин смертельных случаев среди онкологических заболеваний во всем мире. [1] Оценки ВОЗ показывают, что к 2025 году будет выявляться более миллиона новых случаев рака печени. Первичный рак печени является шестым наиболее распространенным заболеванием среди злокачественных новообразований в мире и находится на четвертом месте среди всех онкологических заболеваний по смертности. Гепатоцеллюлярная карцинома печени (ГЦК) находится на пятом месте по распространенности среди мужчин и на седьмом среди женщин. [3]

Раннее выявление ГЦК и назначение адекватной терапии имеют решающее значение для увеличения выживаемости, а также улучшения качества жизни пациента. Самым главным приоритетом при выборе лечения является наиболее ранняя диагностика и решение дальнейшей тактики ведения. Наиболее часто применяемые методы лечения: трансартериальная химиоэмболизация (ТАХЭ), радиочастотная катетерная абляция (РЧА), резекция, Сорафениб. Выбор метода лечения зависит от стадии заболевания. В случае поздней диагностики применяются местное и паллиативное лечение. [2]

Цель. Провести анализ клинических и эпидемиологических особенностей распространения гепатоцеллюлярной карциномы печени (ГЦК) в Республике Казахстан.

Методы. Был проведен ретроспективный анализ результатов клинического исследования 170 пациентов, госпитализированных в Национальный институт кардиологии и внутренних болезней (НИИ К и ВБ) и медицинского центра "Эвелина" за период 2011 – 2021г. г. Алматы. Также были проанализированы данные национального онкологического регистра Республики Казахстан за период с 2011г. по 2021г.

Критерии включения и исключения. Были выбраны клинические случаи, которые в точности описывали пол, возраст, расу, этиологию заболевания, класс тяжести, выбранные методы лечения. Все случаи, которые не включали индикаторы поиска, были исключены.

Сбор информации. Пациенты были сгруппированы по соответствующим категориям, и из каждого клинического случая была извлечена следующая информация: пол, возраст, раса, этиология заболевания, класс тяжести, выбранные методы лечения.

Анализ. Был проведен подсчет и математический анализ, высчитана медиана, выведено процентное соотношение.

Характеристика результатов.

Эпидемиология. За указанный период в национальном онкологическом регистре Республики Казахстан было зарегистрировано 5070 пациентов с гепатоцеллюлярной карциномой печени (ГЦК), что соответствует 13 - ому месту среди всех онкологических заболеваний в стране на 2021 год. У большинства из них была 4 стадия (42,2%) заболевания, за которой следовали 1-2 стадии (32,2%) и 3 стадия (25,6%). Среди 170 пациентов, находившихся на стационарном лечении в НИИ К и ВБ: мужчин – 100 (58,8%), женщин – 70 (41,2%). Возраст пациентов составил от 35 до 85 лет. Средний возраст – 60 ± 8 лет. Возраст от 30 – 50 лет (11,8%), от 50 – 70 лет (69,4%), от 70 – 90 лет (18,8%). Соотношение мужчин и женщин в зависимости от этиологии: хронический гепатит В (ХГВ) – 64,2%/35,8% (средний возраст – 62,1), хронический гепатит С (ХГС) – 55,3%/44,7% (средний возраст – 61,8), ХГД – 40,7%/59,4% (средний возраст – 56,8), алиментарный стеатогепатит (АСГ) АСГ – 84,5%/15,6% (средний возраст – 55,8), неалкогольный стеатогепатит (НСГ) – 40%/60 (средний возраст – 67,5%). Так же был проведен анализ расовой принадлежности: азиаты - 134 (78,8%), европейцы – 36 (21,2%).

Этиопатогенез. Был проведен анализ процентного соотношения этиологического фактора ГЦК: хронический гепатит В (ХГВ) – 23%, ХГВ + ХГС – 2%, ХГВ + АСГ – 2,8%, хронический гепатит С (ХГС) – 27,5%, ХГС + АСГ – 8%, хронический гепатит Д (ХГД) – 21,5%, алиментарный стеатогепатит (АСГ) – 4%, неалкогольный стеатогепатит (НСГ) – 4,2%, Криптогенный цирроз – 7%

В большинстве случаев гепатоцеллюлярная карцинома печени (ГЦК) диагностировалась при циррозе печени: класс тяжести по шкале Чайлд-Пью В (41,1%), реже – класс А (31,1%) и С (24,7%).

Выбранные методы лечения. Из 170 случаев у 60 пациентов (35,3%) были предприняты определенные методы лечения: РЧА - 4 человека - 6,6%; ТАХЭ - 14 человека - 23,5%; Сорафениб - 7 человек - 11,6%; Хай-Фу терапия - 2 человека - 3,3%; Резекция сегментов печени - 13 человек - 21,7%; Лучевая терапия - 1 человек - 1,7%; ТАХЭ + РЧА - 6 человек - 10%; ТАХЭ + резекция - 2 человека - 3,3%; ТАХЭ + Сорафениб - 6 человек - 10%; Резекция + Сорафениб - 1 человек - 1,7%; ТАХЭ+Резекция+ Сорафениб - 2 человека - 3,3%; ТАХЭ + РЧА + Резекция+ Сорафениб - 2 человека - 3,3%.

Заключение. В результате исследования было доказано, что гепатоцеллюлярная карцинома печени (ГЦК) преимущественно встречается у мужчин – азиатов средней возрастной категории, и частым этиологическим фактором является осложнение вирусных гепатитов: хронический гепатит С (ХГС) – 27,5%, хронический гепатит В (ХГВ) – 23%, хронический гепатит Д (ХГД) – 21,5%, с тяжестью по шкале Чайлд-Пью В (41,1%), реже – класс А (31,1%) и С (24,7%).

Эти данные еще раз подчеркивают важность и актуальность выбранного заболевания и требуют дальнейшего изучения и сравнения с данными других государств, так как рост онкологических заболеваний увеличивается с каждым годом, и является одной из самых главных проблем современной медицины.

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PERFORMANCE CULTURE OF THE FUTURE MUSIC ESTRADE SPECIALIST IN THE PIANO CLASS

Abeltayeva Zhanel Ertaevna

PhD, associate professor of Kazakh National academy of art named after T.Zhurgenov

The complex and unique world of artistic phenomena in the field of pop arts and performance, marked by a rich palette of means of self-expression, dramatic identification, and empathy, aims the explorer, when analyzing any phenomenon, to identify not only the problem itself, but also to examine it from the point of view of culturological field of scientific knowledge. The performing culture of a professional musician is an essential phenomenon of individual creativity, which is distinct in its artistic conception, on the one hand, and, in a set of artistic and technological possibilities, on the other hand, being formed through the activities of a specialist.

Being secondary to the author's model, performing arts act as a relatively independent artistic activity, the creative essence of which is manifested in the final product, namely, **interpretation**, which comes fruition in the course of **four main stages** - the emergence of a concept, its formation, implementation, verification and evaluation.

Let us briefly characterize the process of interpreting a piece of music in working with piano material in the classroom with future musical stage performers.

First of all, we emphasize that the emergence of an idea is preceded by the choice of a composition, and the search for ideas for its implementation of interpretation. At this stage, it is necessary to determine the guidelines for the essential analysis of the piece, stirring the cognitive interest of students in understanding the main performing tasks in order to make a logical transition to technological methods and means of their implementation with the direct help of the instrument. At the same time, the formation of the artistic concept of mastering music is associated with the stimulation of the intellectual activity of students, bringing out any hidden potentialities and abilities in the pursuit of expressive performance, thereby ensuring the transfer of emotional and semantic message of the author's text. This peculiar feature was noted by N.A. Rimsky-Korsakov, believing that "... the ultimate technical ability to play or sing is inspired by the pursuance of expressiveness, of a greater or lesser extent of creativity in performance, and of subjective expression, emanating from one's own internal need..." [4, p. 105].

Mental playback of a composition has to do with imagination, visual associations, differing in consciousness in working with the text - in reviewing, reading music, committing it to memory, when a combination in the thinking process of several multi-level tasks associated with coordination of hands, fingering, rhythmic pattern, etc. is required. The incarnation of an artistic concept is a translation of mental symbols into sound realities, where performer performs logical operations based on their specific and distinctive features.

Pedagogical demonstration, listening to recordings of the studied piece of music, selection of expressive means and actual work of a piano-player are expedient. In particular, examining issues related to piano art, A. Corto explains, "When working on a piece, the interpreter must perform three actions - rise up to see the terrain, then go down to see and remember everything, and, finally, rise up again, in order to fulfill the distinctive features of music at the time of delivery of the composition. Details only occupy the interpreter in the second stage of the work. At the beginning and at the end of the work, there is an embracing of the whole. [1, p.208].

The last stage in working with students is the verification and evaluation of the implemented plan, when the ultimate artistic outcome is presented.

Achieving the interpretation of a piece of music is the main component of the performing culture of students in the piano class in preparation for estrade music activities. In this regard, the following tasks are of particular importance:

- stimulation of intellectual activity to the emergence of an artistic concept;
- education of psychological stability at the final stage of interpretation.

At the same time, creative tasks include the following:

1. Oral summaries of works – characteristics of the era, main ideas of the composition, distinctive features of formation, specific challenges in piano performance.
2. Mental playback of any popular composition by note.
3. Comparative characteristics of two different performances of the same piece setting out their own interpretation.
4. Analysis of several different interpretations of pieces of music and presentation of one's own views on the stylistic peculiarities of the performance of a composer's music.

The interpreter's tempo and rhythm is the key to comprehending the tempo and rhythm of the composer, which, according to Mozart, "is the most necessary, the most difficult and most important thing in music". Moreover, L.I. Oborin believed that "feeling the pulse in a piece is essential... One must engage in the rhythmic life of music, one must touch its pulse even before they start playing". The correctly found tempo and rhythm of a performer determines the nature and peculiarities of all technical, expressive techniques and means of expressing music.

It should be borne in mind that the essential weapon in the pianist's toolkit of technical means is the expedient arrangement of hands, where each finger is a unique individuality, and all fingers taken together make up a kind of creative team. Diversity of sound – nuancing is also fundamental in performance. Strict compliance with the simplest rules when at the instrument, on the one hand, significantly increases the effectiveness in the art of interpretation, and on the other hand, it allows one to get rid of unwanted injuries and negative emotions in the piano implementation of what was conceived.

Describing the term of "performance culture" of a musical estrade specialist, it should be noted that its content is based on performance thinking in creating an artistic image of a composition, the harmony of methods and skills of performing technique, in combination with an advance taste for art. In the performance culture of a pop musician, there are principles created by the very nature of art - artistry (expressiveness, sincerity "the facts of life"), figurativeness (action in the image of a piece of art), empathy (immersion, getting used to the image), variability and improvisation (variability, fantasy, and creativity), dynamism (activity and independence), drama (tension of action).

The extent of artistic maturity and the achieved level of mastery of the instrument depends on the mastery of the "culture of feelings" of the performer, and creative potential, self-knowledge is a complex joint search for meanings, images, means, etc. In this regard, a certain communicative goal arises - between composer and a piece of music, a teacher - student - empathy - co-creation, where the focus is on feelings, experiences, assessments, values, and the sources are the results of relationships with the surrounding reality.

So, mastering the performance culture as the most important professional quality of a creative personality is the most important problem for all types of activities, including musical and performance in the preparation of a estrade art specialist. The author's performance is, first of all, the comprehension of music from the original source, from its creator. It should only aim at the deepening, development and improvement of those artistic intentions that are recorded or outlined in the piece.

Correlation, interaction in the performance process of conception and implementation has not only a direct, but also a reverse direction - not only the concept determines the

peculiarities of its technical implementation, but also the pianist's technical skill, his or her technological equipment that determine the range of performance potential where the creative expressive element would be released with maximum force. This peculiarity was noted by outstanding teachers/piano players. In particular, G.G. Neuhaus wrote, “The *What* determines the *How*, although in the last analysis the *How* determines the *What* (dialectics) [3, p.14]. K.A. Martinsen pointed out the problem of interdependence between the idea and the manifestation, noting that “technology is and should be a true outward form of revealing what the soul longs for” [2, p.31]. However, he further emphasizes that “...the imagination can only conceive what the body is capable of expressing. And only the part that the body can express can be manifested from this idea, which, again, the body can express. But at the same time, the body can express nothing of essential importance if its skill and mastery have not grown out of an inner spiritual intent” [2, p. 32].

Therefore, the technique should not be the ultimate goal of learning, but it must be the most important factor in the student's artistic development, because it activates the freedom of the performing apparatus, the peculiarities of the thought process.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF MOTIVATION IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Mirzoeva Elvira

Master of Arts (M.A.)

Английский, который все еще сохраняет статус международного языка в нашем современном мире, имеет более широкую репутацию среди других иностранных языков. Одним из важных вопросов в процессе обучения английскому языку как иностранному является развитие у учащихся отличных навыков письма с такими языковыми навыками, как чтение, аудирование и понимание на слух. Развитие устной речи и активизация речевой деятельности при обучении английскому языку в настоящее время стали актуальным вопросом. Для решения этой проблемы ученые и методисты, работающие над улучшением преподавания языков, проводят различные эксперименты. Термин «практическое владение» языком, используемым для обучения английскому языку, следует понимать как понимание мнений других людей и привитие их навыков и привычек. Затем эти навыки формируются и трансформируются в речь.

Исследования показывают, что чтение, аудирование и разговорная речь являются очень важными аспектами любого языка. Эти правила распространяются и на английский язык. Однако, чтобы свободно говорить на этом языке, вам нужно больше практиковаться в разговорной речи. Во многих странах мира целью студентов, изучающих английский язык в высших учебных заведениях, является не изучение английского языка на системном уровне, а применение полученных знаний на практике, умение говорить и писать на английском языке и адекватно понимать мысли и идеи говорящих на этом языке. Что вы можете сделать, чтобы повысить интерес к изучению иностранного языка? Психологи доказали, что интерес следует искать в самом студенте, в сфере его личной мотивации. Подобно тому, как мотив является основой деятельности человека, это также рассматривается как инструмент для стимулирования обучения. Какова может быть цель учителя в этом случае?

Добиться эффективных результатов можно, изучив механизм управления мотивами и грамотно применяя их. Лингвисты предлагают разные подходы к решению этой проблемы, учитывая сложность и многогранность работы. Опираясь на мнение психологов, можно сказать, что при обучении иностранному языку учитель должен стремиться развивать мотивацию во внутреннем мире ученика. Внутренняя мотивация уточняет отношение студента к предмету и обеспечивает совершенствование владения иностранным языком. Успех преподавателя проявляется, когда он создает условия, способствующие практическому овладению каждым языком, отдавая предпочтение такому методу обучения, который позволяет каждому учащемуся проявлять активность и творческие способности.

Мотивация подразделяется на типы:

а) Внутренняя мотивация - предполагает выполнение задачи, потому что это приносит личное удовлетворение.

б) Внешняя мотивация - предполагает выполнение задачи или демонстрацию поведения по внешним причинам, таким как избегание наказания или получение вознаграждения.

То, что учитель может сделать с внешней и внутренней мотивацией, определяется рядом факторов. Вероятно, учитель не может создать мотивацию для ученика, некоторые факторы находятся вне класса (внешние), но учитель явно может влиять на эту мотивацию. Например, если учитель негативно относится к культуре изучаемого языка или не владеет языком, если не ставится никаких целей. Когда

возникают подобные факторы, результат процесса преподавания-обучения не будет очень успешным даже для высоко мотивированных студентов.

Итак, мотивация является средством направления и вдохновения человеческой деятельности в любой области. Энтузиазм, успех — это способ продвинуть мотивацию вперед. На самых первых уроках каждый учитель может задавать ученикам вопросы, чтобы узнать их интересы к иностранному языку. Таким образом, цели студентов, то, что они хотят узнать, и их достижения раскрываются перед ними еще раз.

METAPHORICAL FEATURES IN “MOTHER NIGHT” BY KURT VONNEGUT

Leyla Gojayeva

PhD student, Lecturer, Azerbaijan University of Languages

Metaphor plays an important role in revealing the general and the particular, the objective and the subjective, the universal and the national-specific, being the very phenomenon through which the act of the author's worldview is performed. The worldview reflected in the language is called a linguistic picture of the world. Its study is one of the reliable ways of understanding mentality. The basis for the study of worldview is the text, behind which stands its creator, who owns the system of language. Consequently, to identify individual worldview, the texts created by the author are involved. Each fictional text is a space for the implementation by the given writer of the process of cognition of the picture of the world of nature, the world of animals, his own world. Each writer in his quest to know and explain the world around him, passes it through his own signals, which are expressed by words-concepts through numerous tropes, among which metaphor takes the leading position. The purpose of our study was a stylistic interpretation of examples from the novel by K. Vonnegut "Mother Night", in which the metaphor manifested itself specifically in the creation of specific figurative nominations of the concepts LOVE, WAR.

It should be noted that to the works of K. Vonnegut have recently been addressed more and more often not only by readers, but also by literary scholars and linguists. This interest is due, above all, to the uncommon linguistic personality of the writer himself, as well as to his form of creating artistic images using a variety of linguistic means. This form is peculiar, as is the creative personality of the writer. In the statements of literary critics there is no unified opinion about his creative works. For example, Professor of the University of Illinois Ch. Harris refers them to “absurdism”, the features of absurdism in the works of K. Vonnegut are also seen by the teacher of the University of California J. Kennard. The American linguist P. Reed analyzes the works of K. Vonnegut within the framework of modernism. One of the theorists of the "black humor" school, M. Schultz, finds touches of "black humor" in some of Vonnegut's works. Ordinary readers of the works of K. Vonnegut from various countries are also ambivalent about his work. But almost everyone agrees that the books are grandiose, the style is extraordinary, the compositions are amazing, the language is jerky, the plot is extraordinary, and so on. From a linguistic point of view, we find that the works of K. Vonnegut represent great potential from all points of investigation for further study on linguistic levels. We are interested in the exceptional subtlety of the writer in expressing the concepts of LOVE, WAR, and how, with the help of metaphor, one of the main techniques of expressive influence on the reader, the author expresses his worldview of these concepts. We have reinterpreted the chosen metaphors from the point of view of their creator and from our positions. We came to the conclusion that the picture of the world, created by metaphor as one of the linguistic means, reflects the individual picture of the world in the mind of the writer, which is embodied in the selection of the content elements of the artwork and in the individual use of lexical and stylistic techniques. Many modern researchers of a literary text believe that in its structure and content one can find a model of the world, as the author understands it. The concept of "linguistic picture of the world" refers to the fundamental concepts that reflect the very essence of a man and his relationship with the outside world. Any author-individual world is formed under the influence of certain factors, and their mutual combination determines the unique uniqueness of style. Language is part of culture, and the culture of each nation has its own vision of the world, which is reflected through language. From the point of view of the relationship between language and culture,

Zh. Vardzelashvili interprets the term “linguistic picture of the world” as “the whole set of ideas about the world, historically formed in the minds of a certain linguistic community and reflected in the language”. From the dissertation of E. A. Voronina, we learn that the author's worldview as a principle of approach to the vital material, its comprehension and selection “in the process of artistic creativity not only verbalizes, since the picture of the world is verbalized, becoming linguistic, but also dictates the whole concept, affects the genre and stylistic identity of the created work”. We agree with this position, as in the work of K. Vonnegut “Mother Night”, we note that the metaphor is the predominant linguistic means of conveying the individual worldview of the author. The metaphor represents and verbalizes various concepts, among which we have chosen two, in our opinion, of infinite interest: the concept of “war” and the concept of “love”. Using the examples taken from this novel, we analyze the specificity of the functioning of a metaphor expressing these concepts, and its possibilities in modeling the individual-author's picture of the world of K. Vonnegut. The concept of LOVE (to his wife Helga) is presented by the author with simple metaphors: “nation of two”, “sovereign territory”, “love-drug”, “soul love”, “angel” (about the wife), etc. It should be noted that the metaphor “nation of two” is repeated several times in the novel, once in German, “Das Reich der Zwei”, obviously in order to emphasize the great power of the characters' love, where in the event of the loss of one of the family members, neither the state nor the nation will exist. The following are examples of these metaphors.

“Away from the sovereign territory of our nation of two, we talked like the patriotic lunatics all around us. But it did not count. Only one thing counted – The nation of two. And when that nation ceased to be, I became what I am today and what I always will be, a stateless person». In this example, a specific image of the protagonist's beloved wife is conveyed, where, with the help of metaphors, there is an artistic transformation of the perception of the real sovereign space “sovereign territory” within the “nation of two” family and the geographical space of the entire state. In this way, K. Vonnegut conveys the dedication and sincerity of his character's feelings.

ARTICLES IN FRENCH

Réfiyeva Khouraman Ali

Branche UPEA Shéki (Azerbaïdjan), Professeur de français, Chef enseignant, Orcid: 0000-0001-9887-4619

Key words: Indefinite article, definite article, the partitif article

L'article est un déterminant du nom, il s'accorde en genre et en nombre avec ce nom. C'est l'article qui marque la différence entre un mot virtuel. La définition est proposée par le dictionnaire et un mot intégré dans une réalité donnée.

-vin est un mot masculin. On se situe dans le virtuel, c'est le mot tel qu'il apparaît dans le dictionnaire.

-J'ai bu un excellent vin- on se situe dans le réel.

L'article est un mot-outil propre au nom qui sert à exprimer ses catégories grammaticales.

Le genre – une fille, une auto

Le nombre – la table, les tables, du sable

La détermination ou in détermination – une pomme, la pomme

1. L'emploi des articles en français est une chose extrêmement délicate, surtout pour les étrangers. On ne peut prétendre à des règles absolument strictes, à des classements rigoureux.

2. L'emploi des articles n'est pas tout à fait le même avec les différentes espèces de noms. Nous allons donc considérer à tour de rôle :

a) L'emploi des articles devant les noms communs nombrables ;

b) L'emploi des articles devant les noms communs non nombrables ;

c) L'emploi des articles devant les noms propres.

C'est l'article qui fait qu'un mot de importe quelle catégorie grammaticale (infinitif, participe présent, participe passé, adjectif, pronom, préposition, expression...) passe dans la catégorie du nom.

le rire, un élève, des résumés, la cadette, le rouge et noir etc.

En français il y a trois sortes d'articles : article défini, article indéfini, article partitif

1. Article indéfini- Ceci est une pomme. **Une** pomme ronde, verte, mûre, appétissante.

Première apparition de l'objet „pomme”, première présentation est article indéfini. En même temps, l'article indéfini désigne un représentant d'une classe, et sert à classer l'objet dont il s'agit dans une espèce d'objets auxquels il est en tout pareil. L'emploi de l'article indéfini avec cette valeur grammaticale particulière typique dans les tours **c'est...et ce sont**.

L'emploi de l'article indéfini s'impose devant les noms, désignant des objets concrets, ou des notions, des notions abstraites, accompagnés d'adjectifs qualificatifs ou de noms sans article, car ces types de compléments attributifs ne servent qu'à caractériser les noms, mais ne les déterminent point. Pour cette raison l'article indéfini est souvent employé dans la description et la caractérisation :

Nous nous assîmes sur un banc de pierre. C'était au mois de mai. *Un parfum de fleurs* voltigeait dans les allées propres ; *un bon soleil* glissait entre les feuilles et semait sur nous *de larges gouttes de lumière*.....(Maupassant)

2. Article défini- Lave **la** pomme avant de manger.

Deuxième présentation de l'objet „pomme” reprise du mot **pomme** ; on sait de

quelle pomme il s'agit. C'est l'article défini. Qu'y a-t-il dans cette tarte ? **De la** pomme ou **de la** poire ?

3. L'article partitif :

L'article partitif est dans la langue d'aujourd'hui une espèce d'article indéfini, employé devant les noms non nombrables. C'est le signe grammatical de la nombrabilité en français. De point de vue historique l'article partitif est formé de la préposition **de**, ayant une valeur partitive, et de l'article défini. Mais depuis longtemps la préposition **de** a perdu sa valeur partitive et s'est fondu avec l'article.

En disant **du pain, de la farine**, on ne désigne pas une partie de ces choses, mais la matière qu'elles représentent, prise dans un sens indéterminé, c'est à dire une quantité indéterminée de cette matière.

- Les articles partitifs sont utilisés quand il y a une idée de quantité. Cette quantité n'est pas précisée.
- On utilise également les articles partitifs pour parler de sentiments ou de qualités chez une personne. Ex :

Il a **du** courage et **du** patience. (de la bonté, de la souplesse)

Elle a **de l'**humour et **de l'**autorité.

Ils ont **de la** peine

**DIGITAL PARTICIPATION OF TEACHER TRAINEES - CASE STUDIES OF
KOSTANAY (KAZAKHSTAN)**

Bezhina Viktoriya Valerievna,

PhD, c.ped.sc., associate professor of FL department, Kostanay regional university named after A.Baitursynov

Solovyova Nataliya Anatolievna,

c.ped.sc., associate professor, the head of FL department, Kostanay regional university named after A.Baitursynov

Zhaukina Saule Alimovna,

PhD doctorate, senior lecturer of FL department, Kostanay regional university named after A.Baitursynov

Digital participation of teacher trainees must be realized through the case study method in post-pandemic time transferring the education into blended format. The experiment on forming the participatory readiness of teacher trainees for realization of blended learning included three stages: introductory stage (solving cases on pandemic forced digital education), main stage (simulating cases on possible online education), analytical stage (analysis of the cases used for simulation cases).

The introductory stage included the solving of cases occurred during the pandemic. Ex: organizing group work online via Canva, using TEL for assessment – online criteria, etc. in case format (What will you do if the students refuse to work in groups online? What are the tools for board demonstration?). 68% of students experienced difficulties when stating the tools and variants of group work organizing. The main stage was aimed at demonstrating the cases for future in the form of foresight – What will be effective to use in terms of online and blended learning (goal-setting, methods choosing, tools identification). The cases assist the teacher trainees in their participatory readiness. The analytical stage was carried in the form of the creative examination ('Professional Guidance of the Teacher' discipline containing cases analysis as a final assessment).

As a result, 37 students demonstrated low level of readiness before the experiment (32%) and only 17 students – after the experiment (12% of all students). The role of cases in digital readiness of future trainees is in the transition of students into the active participants of simulations (role-plays, discussions about teaching, learning, choosing methods, upbringing).

Case study method also proved to be effective as a form of final assessment serving as the tool for blended learning. Combining the stages of participatory readiness of teacher trainees encompasses the role of the students as an active agent of digital pedagogical education.

КОМПАРАТИВИСТСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ СВЕТСКОСТИ НА ПРИМЕРЕ ВОСТОКА И ЗАПАДА

Мирзаходжаев Абдулла Абибуллаевич

Международная исламская академия Узбекистана, Тошкент, Узбекистон, ORCID: 0000000321035838

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются теоретико-методологические основы секулярной концепции. Цель исследования состоит в том, чтобы показать преимущества их сравнения с анализом основных теорий, позволяющих определить понятие светскости между религией и религиозным объединением государственного устройства, которое становится сегодня все более актуальным.

Ключевые слова: светский, секулярность, компаративистский.

Annotation: This article analyzes the theoretical and methodological foundations of the secular concept. The purpose of the study is to show the advantages of comparing them with the analysis of the main theories that allow to determine the concept of secularism between religion and religious association of the state structure, which is becoming increasingly relevant today.

Keywords: secular, secular, comparative.

Понятие светскости в обществе западного и восточного социокультурного пространство, важно затронуть суждению гносеологического понимания Востока и Запада.

Российский исследователь философии Гераклита Эфесского Ф.Х. Кессиди описывает Логос следующим образом: «непреходящий, неизменный закон, закономерность или мера изменяющихся вещей», «логос - это «путь вверх и вниз, образующий из единого многое единое» [1, с. 82].

Как известно, на Востоке религия была доминирующим компонентом культуры общества и с самого начала играла важную роль в развитии политической мысли стран Востока. Известные нам государственные религии древности, а также религиозные учения массовых движений протеста против существующих порядков по праву можно назвать первыми формами идеологии восточных государств. В этих учениях сочетались как морально-нравственные, так и собственно-философские, правовые, политические взгляды и концепции представителей того времени.

Различие картин мира Востока и Запада кроется в различных способах организации социальной жизни и представлениях о месте человека в этом мире. В отличие от западного мировоззрения, восточный принцип созерцания, перенятый из древнекитайской мудрости, восходит к следованию естественному порядку вещей, требующему минимальных действий и созерцания для сохранения жизненной силы, тогда как западное мышление основано на практической реализации идеи активного преобразования природы и социума. Предпосылки логического обоснования миропорядка, подчиненного всеобщему закону природы, сложились в античной философии, затем идея становления человека мыслящего раскрывается в эпоху Возрождения и окончательно утверждается в европейской культуре Нового времени - периоде индустриального общества.

Основное представление о цивилизации и «цивилизационном» было выработано в XVII веке французскими философами в рамках бинарного противостояния «цивилизация - варварство». Это послужило основой доминирования Европейской цивилизации и практики передела мира без учета мнений и желаний любых неевропейских культур [2, с.48].

Ограничение исследования парадигмы Восток-Запад не может сегодня выстраиваться по географическому распределению, разделению на «мы» - представители высокой культуры Запада и на «другие», в дихотомии «мы и они» и другие принципы размежевания двух цивилизации. Многими мировыми деятелями и учеными неоднократно декларируется идея о том, что не может быть разделения мира, сегодня в мире цивилизованного человека взаимоотношения должны выстраиваться на диалоге двух культур - западной и восточной. Тезой всего мирового сообщества сегодня является призыв к объединению цивилизаций и провозглашение социально-культурного развития в сторону глобализации и угманизма. В современном цивилизованном мире понятие «разделение» так же не допустимо ставить в один ряд с «ограничением» мира на восточный и западный. Характерным признаком единения мира является показатель уровня цивилизационного развития народов и культуры.

Профессор Колумбийского Университета Альфред Степан (A. Stepan) говорит о двух моделях секулярности: модель: разделения («separationist») и модель взаимного уважения и взаимной поддержки («respect all support all»)7 К первой модели он относит такие страны как США, Турция, Франция, а ко второй модели - Индию, Индонезию, Сенегал [3, с.4].

Следует понимать, что исследования типологии государств только по критерию светскости формально, так как эти модели не отражают действительного положения дел и реальной ситуации. Любая классификация описывает набор параметров или признаков, характеризующих в своей совокупности набор некие гипотетические объекты или модели, каждая из свойства реального объекта.

В материале, посвящённой сравнительному анализу секуляризма, как правило, выделяется два основных типа светскости в странах Запада: французская модель, распространённая в странах латинского христианства, и англо-саксонская модель, наиболее последовательно реализованная в США.

В отличие от стран латинского христианства, в англо-протестантской культурной области, и в особенности в Соединённых Штатах, отсутствуют строгие разграничительные линии между религией и секулярными сферами социальной жизни.

Среди незападных форм светскости одной из наиболее интересных и своеобразных является её индийская модель. Индийская модель не предполагает возведения стены между государством и религией, публичным и частным.

В странах исламского мира не сформировалась аналогичная странам Запада идея секуляризма как отделения религии и церкви от государства по той простой причине, что в исламе государство и религия не отделимы друг от друга, так как является единой системой норм.

«Исламская и европейская правовые культуры не только позитивно взаимодействуют, но и конкурируют друг с другом. Это проявляется на уровне применения и толкования законодательства, построенного по определенной правовой модели. В частности, профессиональное правосознание в большинстве мусульманских стран, очевидно, тяготеет к европейской правовой культуре, а массовое- продолжает в целом ориентироваться на традиционные исламские ценности» [4, с.81].

Общим принципом сравнительного анализа моделей в странах Востока и Запада должно быть выявление сходств и различий в проведении идеологического и правового разделения государства и религии. В дискуссиях научного сообщества проводятся исследования проблематики «религия и государство» и их взаимодействие в условиях той или иной страны. Западный тип светскости пытается вступить в диалог с религиозными ценностями, определить формы бесконфликтного или наименее конфликтного сосуществования и ними. Мусульманское право ориентировано на

всестороннее участие религии в социальной и политической жизни страны. Светскость здесь фактически сводится лишь к послаблениям в соблюдении религиозного закона. Иными словами, секуляризируется государство (его институты), но преобразования общества на принципах светскости не происходит, и обозримой перспективе ислам продолжит выполнять функции универсального регулятора отношений внутри общины.

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MORPHO-FUNCTIONAL STATE OF GRASS CARP (CTENOPHARYNGODON IDELLA) FROM KAPSHAGAY RESERVOIR

Tastan Dinara Abaikyzy

MSC of al-Farabi Kazakh National University

Scientific supervisor: Doctor of Biological Sciences, Professor Shalakhmetova T.M.

The toxicological state of the Kapshagay reservoir is a relevant problem. Studies demonstrated the toxicological state and the level of anthropogenic pollution of the reservoir. The Kapshagay reservoir is subjected to pollution by heavy metals, both in the spatial and temporal aspects, which is associated with fluctuations in the flow of the river Ile.

The purpose is to conduct a study of the morpho-functional state of the visceral organs of grass carp from the Kapshagay reservoir. According to the results of the previous study, the MPC level was exceeded for copper - from 5.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dm}^3$ to 32 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dm}^3$ (32 MPC), for zinc - from 18 and 21 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dm}^3$ in 2012 and 2018. up to 69 and 75 mcg/dm^3 in 2014 and 2019 respectively.

The research material is the grass carp (*Ctenopharyngodon Idella*) and for this study, a histological research method was used. For histological analysis, immediately after the catch, the gills and liver of carp with signs of anomalies and those devoid of external manifestations of the pathological process were selected.

Studies show that in the organs of carp, heavy metals are mainly accumulated in the liver (iron (Fe), zinc (Zn), copper (Cu), and lead (Pb)) and muscles (chromium (Cr)). Exceeding the MPC for iron (Fe) was noted in carp - in the gills, heart, liver, and gonads; For zinc (Zn), MPC is exceeded in carp - in the heart and liver.

Morphological study of the gills. The lamella epithelial lining reacts to dissolved lead creating tissue osmoregulatory imbalance. The observed changes in gills such as hyperplasia, lamellar fusion, epithelial necrosis, and edema were generally attributed to the toxic effects of lead. Similar alterations in the gills have also been reported in the fish exposed to metals.

Pathological findings in the liver included cytoplasmic vacuolation, cellular degeneration, swelling of hepatocytes, and focal necrosis. Histology of the heart included chronic inflammation, leucocyte infiltration, and edema of muscle bundles. Heavy metals, especially lead induce gills, liver, and muscle damage as indicated by the elevation of histopathological alterations, the decline of the enzyme, and antioxidant activity.

In conclusion, the study revealed histopathological alterations and morphometric evidence in the visceral organs of grass carp. In addition, histological and morphological alterations were observed in all parts of the Kapshagay reservoir, even in the basins of the river Ile and lake Balkhash.

DEVELOPMENT OF A PROBIOTIC DRUG FOR THE PREVENTION OF POULTRY DISEASES

Alina Nurgazina

PhD student of Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan

Aliya Kudaibergenova.

PhD student of Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan

Nazerke Begdildayeva

PhD students of Almaty Technological University, Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan

Currently, we are observing a tendency towards an increase in the share of probiotic drugs and their replacement for antibiotics in the veterinary sector of agriculture. Since the use of antibiotics in preventive measures leads to the emergence of resistant strains, and also raises consumer concerns about their residues in food products.

The use of probiotics to maintain natural immunity in poultry is relevant. As the recent outbreak of bird flu has shown: according to the chairman of the Committee for Veterinary Control and Supervision of the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Kazakhstan, there are about 46 million birds in Kazakhstan, the percentage of deaths from the outbreak of bird flu is 0.9%.

To create new probiotic products, it is necessary to carry out a directed selection of microorganisms among strains with a special complex of biotechnological properties. At the same time, strains capable of maintaining biochemical activity for a long period are valuable. It is also necessary to consider that functional properties largely depend on the properties of specific strains and their quantities in the product is obtained.

Camel milk and its fermented products, including shubat, are a source of valuable probiotic bacteria. Among the most common representatives of lactic acid bacteria in shubat and camel milk can be found: *Enterococcus spp.*, *Lactococcus spp.*, *Lactobacillus spp.*, *Leuconostoc spp.* On the basis of LLP "Antigen" we isolated strains of the following types of lactic acid bacteria from shubat: *Lactobacillus kefir*, *Lactobacillus casei*, *Enterococcus faecium*.

To create new probiotic products, it is necessary to carry out a directed selection of microorganisms among strains with a special complex of biotechnological properties. When developing a domestic probiotic preparation in the process of selecting functionally active strains of lactic acid microorganisms. Experiments were designed to determine the following indicators: resistance to high concentrations of salt, bile, various pH values, resistance to pepsin, phenol, antibiotics: ampicillin, gentamycin, kanamycin, erythromycin, tetracycline and antagonistic activity against pathogenic and opportunistic microflora. As a result of this work strains that showed high tolerance were selected for further study.

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THE THEORY OF MULTICULTURALISM IN MODERN SOUTH KOREA

Aidarova Aruzhan

4th year student of the Department of Oriental Studies, Faculty of International Relations,
L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University

Relevance of the topic. Since time immemorial, people have been extremely concerned with their identity, and have learned to rally with each other for the sake of achieving common goals and protection. Over time, the fundamental concept took root that someone is “ours” for someone, and someone is “alien” - one that does not belong to the local community and, therefore, poses an external threat. This principle has been preserved for centuries and has become so much a part of our daily life, soon giving rise to several key theories and concepts in modern sociology and political science. The work will attempt to examine in detail the theory of multiculturalism as a phenomenon, and then consider this phenomenon in the context of another region. In our case, South Korea.

The object of this study is the theory of Multiculturalism in general, its aspects and particular impact on South Korean society.

The subject of this study is the analysis of the multicultural policy of South Korea since its inception in early 2000, the influence of the theory on the social and cultural development of the state.

The purpose of this work is to analyze the impact of multicultural policy on South Korean society.

To achieve this goal, it is necessary to solve the following **tasks**:

- Comprehensively consider the historical and cultural background of the influence of multiculturalism on society.
- Analyze the theory of Multiculturalism and all previous research.
- Research and analyze available interviews and articles.
- Identify clear examples of how Koreans themselves treat migrants and refugees.
- Analyze real cases of discrimination against migrants and refugees over the past ten years.
- Consider the dynamics of changes in the attitudes of South Koreans towards migrants and refugees.
- Analyze the available articles of the Korean media.

Discussion: At the present time, when the borders between states are gradually blurring, and states are taking confident steps towards a global united world, the theory of multiculturalism, and in general cultural pluralism, is one of the most relevant topics not only around the world, but also in South Korea. At the moment, issues and problems of migration, refugees and acceptance of other cultures are being actively raised in the mentioned state. Due to the relatively recent hardline policy of the One Nation, South Korea is only taking the first steps towards accepting this phenomenon, as evidenced by numerous programs, active protests, and even anti-immigration movements.

Results: Today it is widely known that in the period of active globalization in the world it is impossible to abstract from culture, since it is an integral part of any society. Considering everything that was mentioned above, one can come to the conclusion that multiculturalism in theory is only one big critique towards liberalism, but this is not so. Mono-ethnic cultures, in which the principles of isolation are deeply rooted, are a prime example of what multiculturalism specifically brings to the world. People tend to judge the world around them only from the point of view of their single arrangements, without paying attention to the point of view from which someone else will consider it. Coexisting with

representatives of other cultures, people learn to live differently, share experiences, and literally expand their horizons.

Conclusions: In the case of South Korea, this country still has a long way to go to establish a stable and loyal to all multicultural policies, because due to historical and geographical features in the form of long isolation and colonization by the Japanese Empire, South Korea was subject to strong nationalist views, which do not allow them to evaluate foreigners as equals.

ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ НА УРОКАХ МАТЕМАТИКИ КАК СРЕДСТВО САМОРЕАЛИЗАЦИИ УЧАЩИХСЯ

Кокажаева Амангуль Базарбековна

к.б.н., и.о.ассоц.проф. кафедры «Математика», Казахский национальный женский педагогический университет, г.Алматы, Казахстан

Жексембинова Айжан Бекбергеновна

8D01505-докторант 2 курса кафедры «Математика», Казахский национальный женский педагогический университет, г.Алматы, Казахстан

Рапагат Жамиля

Магистрант 1 курса кафедры «Математика», Казахский национальный женский педагогический университет, г.Алматы, Казахстан

Таштемирова Салтанат

Магистрант 1 курса кафедры «Математика», Казахский национальный женский педагогический университет, г.Алматы, Казахстан

Аннотация.

В статье рассматривается структура интегрированных уроков, преимущества интеграции на уроках и методах их реализации.

Ключевые слова: интеграция, интегрированные уроки, математика, математические понятия, межпредметные связи.

Abstract.

The article discusses the structure of integrated lessons, the advantages of integration in the classroom and methods of their implementation.

Keywords: integration, integrated lessons, mathematics, mathematical concepts, interdisciplinary connections.

На современном этапе характерными направлениями развития системы образования являются: гуманизация, дифференциация, профилирование, вариативность, индивидуализация образовательного процесса. Эти процессы определяют право каждого учащегося школы выбирать путь или уровень образования, который позволит максимально развить его способности и интересы. Уровень образования и профессиональной подготовки выпускников школы должен соответствовать социальному заказу. Основой необходимости повышения качества образовательного процесса в школе является интеграция учебных предметов.

Интеграция отражает общую и всестороннюю тенденцию установления связей между информацией, образованием, наукой, а также обеспечивает их целостность и целостную структуру, охватывающую все компоненты в диалектическом единстве. Процесс интеграции представляет собой объединение ранее выделенных частей и элементов системы в единое целое на основе их взаимозависимости и взаимодополняемости [1].

В школьном курсе математика занимает особое место в развитии и воспитании мышления и общего образования учащихся. Преподавание математики в школе:

а) учит учащихся осваивать характерные для математики средства познания окружающей среды;

б) помогает развивать математические знания учащихся, применять их в реальной жизни;

в) знакомит с практическим применением математики, способствует пониманию ими основных направлений и значения научно-технического процесса;

г) способствует формированию логического мышления и познавательной деятельности учащихся, развитию представлений о пространстве, а также формированию творческих способностей;

д) математическая наука создает благоприятные условия для формирования научного отношения ученика к миру, культуры труда, воспитанию таких качеств, как пунктуальность, последовательность, самостоятельность. Необходимость воспитания личности и роль математического образования на современном этапе определяют цель обучения математике в школе. Методологической основой определения цели обучения математике является учение о формировании всесторонне развитой активной личности общества, взаимосвязи научного подхода и практики.

Возможность интеграции обеспечивается тем, что в математике и смежных дисциплинах изучаются однотипные понятия (например, вектор в математике и физике; координаты в математике, физике, географии; уравнения в математике, физике, биологии, географии), а через математические средства выражения зависимостей между величинами (формулы, графики, таблицы, уравнения, неравенства и их системы) и многие другие предметы объясняются тем, что используются при обучении. Взаимопроникновение знаний и методов в различные учебные предметы отражает современные тенденции развития науки, формирует научное мировоззрение учащихся [2].

Интеграция обучения является одним из направлений активного поиска новых педагогических решений, способствующих развитию творческого потенциала образовательных организаций и отдельных педагогов для эффективного воздействия на учащихся. Интеграция как явление возникла, прежде всего, в фундаментальной и прикладной науке. Как и естественнонаучные дисциплины, использование интеграции с математикой в процессе обучения дает хорошие результаты. В тех случаях, когда возникают трудности с усвоением школьного курса математики, целесообразно использовать интегрированные уроки, на основе которых дети активно участвуют в образовательном процессе. Форма проведения интегрированных уроков позволяет четко ее планировать, творчески использовать изученный материал по математике и другим предметам, разрабатывать задания, серьезно и много трудиться учителям, видеть и оценивать результаты своей работы.

Ведущей тенденцией развития образования является реализация компетентного подхода к обучению с формированием функциональной грамотности учащихся. Математическая грамотность характеризуется уровнем "математической компетентности", который определяется как совокупность знаний, умений, опыта и способностей человека, обеспечивающих успешное решение задач, требующих применения математики [3].

Междисциплинарная интеграция дает большие возможности для развития и повышения интереса старшеклассников к решению математических задач. Интеграция, по мнению В. Г. Иванова, не только взаимосвязана, но и укрепляет взаимную интеграцию учебных предметов друг в друга, способствует целостному и системному познанию окружающего мира. Процесс интеграции представляет собой высокую форму реализации междисциплинарных связей на качественно новом этапе обучения.

Новые стандарты обязывают каждого учащегося выявлять и развивать свои образовательные способности, достигать не только предметных, но и личностных результатов. В рамках изучения отдельных учебных предметов невозможно формирование ключевых компетенций, обеспечивающих обучающимся гибкость и адаптивность по отношению к сегодняшнему обществу. Только в результате совместного изучения всех предметов общего образования у учащихся основные

компетенции формируются как основа способности к обучению. Применение системного подхода к теории и практике обучения свидетельствует о возможности формирования мышления через интеграцию знаний [4].

В настоящее время идеи интеграции стали внедряться в школьную практику большими темпами. Интегрированный урок-это любой урок со структурой, если для его проведения привлекаются результаты анализа изучаемого материала методами других наук и учебных дисциплин. Интеграция в современной педагогической науке определяется как необходимое условие учебного процесса. Используются различные методы интеграции. Интеграция показывает ученику взаимосвязь отдельных частей мира как системы. Известно, что источником интеграции являются междисциплинарные связи, которые являются объединяющим фактором формирования содержания и структуры учебных дисциплин.

В последние годы на уроках математики было проведено множество исследований, которые показали, что актуализация межпредметной интеграции оказывает положительное влияние на обучение.

В дополнение к обучению, углубленное изучение сильных связей и научных концепций открывает картину, которая помогает учащимся рассматривать концепции в более широком контексте. В той или иной степени это связано с тем, что учащиеся должны использовать междисциплинарные интегрированные знания при решении задач, углубленно рассматривать проблемы с разных точек зрения при актуализации межпредметной интеграции на уроках математики [5].

Изучение математики на основе междисциплинарной интеграции способствует интеллектуальному развитию учащегося, формированию его умений.

Интегрированные уроки имеют много преимуществ, поскольку они решают не только общеобразовательные задачи, которые позволяют учащимся сформировать более целостное представление о мире. Отличная возможность применения различных технологий, методов, форм на интегрированных занятиях – позволяет решить еще одну важную задачу в условиях школы – это здоровьесберегающий подход в обучении. Использование методов интеграции в организации учебного процесса способствует созданию условий психологического комфорта, предполагающих наличие атмосферы творчества, сотрудничества и взаимопомощи, возможности самовыражения и самореализации, успешное развитие личности и сохранение здоровья детей. Эффективность интегрированного образования зависит от правильного, педагогически обоснованного выбора форм организации обучения, обеспечиваемого глубоким и всесторонним анализом развивающих, воспитательных возможностей каждого из них. Интеграция между дисциплинами возможна только при наличии здорового климата в учительском коллективе, при их плодотворном сотрудничестве, основанном на взаимопонимании и взаимоуважении. В свою очередь, для проведения интегрированного урока необходимо учитывать следующие условия: прежде всего учитель должен выбрать объект исследования на уроке и тщательно проанализировать содержание урока. В процессе реализации урока необходимо продумать технологию самостоятельной образовательной деятельности учащихся. Учитель должен использовать методы проблемного обучения, так как это активизирует умственную деятельность учащихся на всех этапах урока. Продуманное сочетание индивидуальной и групповой форм работы также является неотъемлемой частью интегрированного занятия. Конечно, не следует забывать учитывать возрастные психологические особенности учащихся и их направленность на здоровый образ жизни. Реализация интегрированного урока также невозможна без знания его видов и форм. Такие занятия

дают наилучшие результаты, учителя находят различные задания, сортируют их по своим связям с разными предметами [6].

В заключении хотим отметить, что интеграция как средство обучения способствует формированию системности и целостности в знаниях, умениях, навыках учащихся, их отношении к миру, культуре и ее ценностям. Самое большое счастье учителя – видеть радостную улыбку детей от их маленьких открытий, которые они делают на наших интегрированных уроках.

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